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ABDALLA KARWAN RADHA ABDALLA

Full Name

Scientific adviser:

Prof., Doc. of Ph. and Math
Sciences, Associate Professor
position, uch. degree, uch. rank

 25.05.21
signature, date

A.N. SERGEEV
initials, surname

Head department:

Ph.D., Associate professor
position, uch. degree, uch. rank

 25.05.21
signature, date

S.V. GALAEV
initials, surname

Saratov 2021

Introduction

The theory of *group representations* deals with the classification of homomorphisms of the abstract group G into linear transformation groups or matrix groups. This paper develops the theory of representations of finite groups in finite-dimensional vector spaces. The field K over which vector spaces are defined is often (not always) taken as complex numbers. Mathematical interpretation is at a level between representation theory for physicists and representation theory for mathematicians.

In the first section of the first chapter, we introduce the basic definitions of group representation theory and provide examples to illustrate them. The theory of representations of finite Abelian groups is presented in full, and we are also talking about the characters of representations, Schur's lemma, etc.

In the second chapter, we study irreducible representations of the symmetric group S_n based on the Young symmetrizer technique.

The third chapter discusses a new look at obtaining a Young symmetrizer for a symmetric group.

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Chapter 1

Understanding Linear Representations and Representation Characters

1.1 Understanding Linear Representations

In this section, we outline the general properties of linear representations of finite groups and focus on characters.

1.1.1 Definitions

Let V be a vector space over the field $\mathbb{C}$ of complex numbers, and let $GL(V)$ be the group of its linear isomorphisms over the same field onto itself. Each element of the group $GL(V)$ is, by definition, a linear mapping a of the space V into itself, which has an inverse a^{-1} , this inverse is linear. In the case when the space V has a finite basis (e_i) of n elements, any linear mapping $a : V \rightarrow V$ is given by a square matrix (a_{ij}) of order n . The coefficients a_{ij} are here complex numbers, they are obtained by expressing the images $a(e_j)$ in terms of the basis (e_i) :

$$a(e_j) = \sum_i a_{ij} e_i.$$

Moreover, the mapping a is an isomorphism if and only if the determinant $\det(a) = \det(a_{ij})$ is nonzero. The group $GL(V)$ is thus identifiable with the group of *invertible square matrices of order n* .

Now let G be some finite group. A *linear representation* of the group G in the space V is an arbitrary homomorphism ρ of the group G into the group $GL(V)$. In other words, this is a mapping to each element $s \in G$ of an element $\rho(s)$ of the group $GL(V)$, under which the equality

$$\rho(st) = \rho(s)\rho(t) \quad \text{for all } s, t \in G.$$

[Often we will also write ρ_s instead of $\rho(s)$.] Note that the following relations follow from the previous equality:

$$\rho(1) = 1, \quad \rho(s^{-1}) = \rho(s)^{-1}.$$

When ρ is given, the space V is called the *representation space* of the group G (or even simply, by abuse of language, a *representation* of the group G). In what follows, we restrict ourselves to the case when the space V has *finite dimension*. This is not a very severe restriction. Indeed, for most applications, one is interested in dealing with a *finite number of elements* x_i of the space V , and one can always find some *subrepresentation* (in the sense of defined

later, cf. 1.1.4) of finite dimension, which containing elements x_i : it suffices to take the subspace of the space V generated by the images $\rho_s(x_i)$ of elements x_i .

Therefore, we will assume that the space V is finite-dimensional, and let n be its dimension. We will also call the number n the *degree* of the considered representation. Let (e_i) be a basis of the space V and R_s the matrix of the automorphism ρ_s with respect to this basis. Then

$$\det(R_s) \neq 0, \quad R_{st} = R_s \cdot R_t, \quad s, t \in G.$$

If by $r_{ij}(s)$ we denote the coefficients of the matrix R_s , then the second formula can be rewritten as

$$r_{ik}(st) = \sum_j r_{ij}(s) \cdot r_{jk}(t).$$

Conversely, the definition of invertible matrices $R_s = (r_{ij}(s))$, satisfying the previous identities, defines some linear representation ρ of the group G in the space V : this is what it means to give a representation "in matrix form".

1.1.2 Basic examples

(a) Suppose that the group G is defined as a permutation group of some set X . We denote by $x \mapsto sx$ the substitution corresponding to the element $s \in G$. For V we take the vector space of complex-valued functions on X and for each function $f \in V$ and each element $s \in G$ we define the function $\rho_s f$ by the formula

$$\rho_s f(x) = f(s^{-1}x)$$

(the function $\rho_s f$ is in the obvious sense the image of the function f with the substitution s). It is clear that $\rho_s f$ depends linearly on f , that is, ρ_s is some automorphism of the space V and, moreover, $\rho_{st} = \rho_s \circ \rho_t$. Thus, we obtain some linear representation of the group G in the space V .

(b) Each representation of degree 1 is a homomorphism $\rho : G \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^*$ of the group G into the multiplicative group of complex numbers $\mathbb{C}^*$. Since every element of the (finite) group G is of finite order, the values of ρ_s providing ρ are roots of one; in particular, $|\rho_s| = 1$. If we put $\rho_s = 1$ for all $s \in G$, then we get some representation of the group G , which is called *unit* (or *trivial*) *representation*.

(c) Let g denote the order of the group G and V is a vector space of dimension g with basis $(e_t)_{t \in G}$ indexed by elements t of the group G . For each $s \in G$, we then define a linear mapping ρ_s of the space V into itself, which sends the element e_t to the element e_{st} . It is easy to check that in this way we obtain some linear representation, which is called the *regular representation of the group G* . Its degree is equal to the order of the group G . Note that $e_s = \rho_s(e_1)$ and, therefore, the images of the element e_1 form a basis of the space V . Conversely, if the representation space W of some representation ρ of the group G contains a vector w such that the elements $\rho_s(w), s \in G$, form a basis of the space W , then this representation is isomorphic to the regular representation (the isomorphism $\tau : V \rightarrow W$ is given by the formula $\tau(e_s) = \rho_s(w)$).

(d) More generally, suppose that G acts on a finite set X . This means that for each $s \in G$ a permutation $x \mapsto sx$ of the element X is given, satisfying the identity condition

$$1x = x, \quad s(tx) = (st)x, \quad \text{if } s, t \in G, \quad x \in X.$$

Let V be a vector space with basis $(e_x)_{x \in X}$, indexed by elements of X . For $s \in G$ let ρ_s be the linear map of V into V that sends e_x to e_{sx} ; a linear representation of G , so the resulting representation is called the *permutation representation* associated with X .

1.1.3 Isomorphic representation

Let ρ^1 and ρ^2 be two representations of the group G in the spaces V_1 and V_2 , respectively, and the dimensions of the spaces V_1 and V_2 are the same, that is, the spaces V_1 and V_2 are isomorphic. Representations V_1 and V_2 are called *isomorphic* (equivalent, similar) if $\vartheta\rho^1 = \rho^2\vartheta$, where ϑ is an isomorphic mapping of the space V_1 onto V_2 . (It is clear that isomorphic representations have the same degrees.)

Equality $\vartheta\rho^1 = \rho^2\vartheta$ means that $\vartheta\rho^1(a) = \rho^2(a)\vartheta$ for any element $a \in G$, and this, in turn, means that for any vector $x \in V_1$

$$(1.1) \quad \vartheta\rho^1(a)x = \rho^2(a)\vartheta x.$$

Let us explain the "geometric meaning" of the last equality. Let $x \in V_1$ and $y = \vartheta x \in V_2$. Then the equality (1.1) means that $\vartheta\rho^1(a)x = \rho^2(a)y$, that is, what if

$$x \leftrightarrow y$$

(the vector $x \in V_1$ corresponds to the vector $y \in V_2$ under the isomorphic mapping ϑ of the space V_1 to V_2), then $\rho^1(a)x \longleftrightarrow \rho^2(a)y$, i.e. the images $\rho^1(a)x$ and $\rho^2(a)y$ of the elements x and y for any $a \in G$ also correspond to each other under the mapping ϑ :

$$\vartheta(\rho^1(a)x) = \rho^2(a)y.$$

In other words, it makes no difference whether to first map the vector $x \in V_1$ by means of ϑ into the space V_2 , and then apply the transformation corresponding to the element $a \in G$ to the resulting vector ϑx , or do it in reverse order; here the following "commutative diagram" is executed:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & \vartheta & \\ & \downarrow & \\ \rho^1(a) & x & \longrightarrow \vartheta(x) \\ & \downarrow & \downarrow \rho^2(a) \\ & \vartheta & \end{array}$$

$$\rho^1(a)x \longrightarrow \vartheta\rho^1(a)x = \rho^2(a)\vartheta(x)$$

An isomorphic mapping ϑ of the space V_1 onto V_2 can be given by a square (nondegenerate) matrix H . Then for each $a \in G$ the corresponding matrices $\rho^1(a)$ and $\rho^2(a)$ of isomorphic representations ρ^1 and ρ^2 are related by the relation $H\rho^1(a) = \rho^2(a)H$, which can be rewritten as

$$\rho^1(a) = H^{-1}\rho^2(a)H.$$

This means that if the space V_1 is identified with the space V_2 (isomorphic to it) and the matrix H considered as a transition matrix to a new basis in this space, then $\rho^1(a)$ and $\rho^2(a)$ are matrices of the same operator, taken in different bases.

1.1.4 Subrepresentations

Let $\rho : G \rightarrow GL(V)$ be a linear representation and let W be a vector subspace of V . Suppose that the subspace W is *stable* with respect to the action of the group G (we say also "invariant") in the representation ρ , that is, for each element $x \in W$ all elements of the form $\rho_s(x), s \in G$, also belong to the subspace W . Then the restriction ρ_s^w of the automorphism ρ_s to W is an automorphism of this subspace and obviously $\rho_{st}^w = \rho_s^w \circ \rho_t^w$. Thus, $\rho^w : G \rightarrow GL(W)$ is a linear representation of the group G in the space W . W is said to be a *subrepresentation* of V .

Example 1.1.1 Consider the regular representation of the group G in the space V , and take W as the one-dimensional subspace of the space V generated by the element $x = \sum_{s \in G} e_s$. Then $\rho_s(x) = x$ for all $s \in G$, whence it follows that W defines a subrepresentation of V , which is isomorphic to the identity representation.

Let V be a vector space, and let W and W' be two subspaces of V . The space V is called the *direct sum* of W and W' if each vector $x \in V$ can be written uniquely as $x = w + w'$, where $w \in W$ and $w' \in W'$; this is equivalent to the intersection of $W \cap W'$ being zero and $\dim V = \dim W + \dim W'$. Then we write $V = W \oplus W'$ and say that W' is complement to the subspace $W \subset V$. The mapping ρ that assigns each vector $x \in V$ to its component w from the subspace W is called the *projection* of the space V onto the subspace W , (associated with the direct decomposition $V = W \oplus W'$) the image of p is the entire subspace W and $p(x) = x$ for each vector $x \in W$. Conversely, if some linear mapping p of V into itself satisfying these properties, then the space V , as is easy to see, is represented as a direct sum of the image W and the kernel W' (i.e., the set of those vectors $x \in V$ for which $p(x) = 0$) is the mapping p , and p is a projection. This method establishes a one-to-one correspondence between the projections of the space V onto the subspace W and the complements W' to the subspace $W \subset V$.

Theorem 1.1.2 Let $\rho : G \rightarrow GL(V)$ be a linear representation of the group G in the space V , and let W be a vector subspace in V that is invariant under G . Then there is a complement W^0 of W in V , which is also invariant under G .

Proof: Let W' be an arbitrary complement to W in V , and let p be the corresponding projection of V onto W . Consider the averaging p^0 of the conjugates of the projection p under the action of elements of the group G :

$$p^0 = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \rho_t \cdot p \cdot \rho_t^{-1} \quad (\text{where } g \text{ is the group order } G).$$

Since p maps V to W and ρ_t preserves W , we see that p^0 maps V to W ; we have $\rho_t^{-1}x \in W$ for $x \in W$, whence

$$p \cdot \rho_t^{-1}x = \rho_t^{-1}x, \quad \rho_t \cdot p \cdot \rho_t^{-1}x = x \text{ and } p^0x = x.$$

Thus, p^0 is the projection of V onto W corresponding to some complement W^0 of W . In addition, we have

$$\rho_s \cdot p^0 = p^0 \cdot \rho_s \quad \text{for all } s \in G.$$

Indeed, calculating $\rho_s \cdot p^0 \cdot \rho_s^{-1}$, we found:

$$\rho_s \cdot p^0 \cdot \rho_s^{-1} = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \rho_s \cdot \rho_t \cdot p \cdot \rho_t^{-1} \cdot \rho_s^{-1} = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \rho_{st} \cdot p \cdot \rho_{st}^{-1} = p^0.$$

If now $x \in W^0$ and $s \in G$, then $p^0x = 0$, therefore, $p^0 \cdot \rho_sx = \rho_s \cdot p^0x = 0$, that is, $\rho_sx \in W^0$, this shows that W^0 is stable for G , and completes the proof. $\blacksquare$

Now let $x \in V$ be an arbitrary vector and w, w^0 its projections onto the subspaces W and W^0 , respectively. Then $x = w + w^0$, whence $\rho_s(x) = \rho_s(w) + \rho_s(w^0)$, and since the subspaces W and W^0 are invariant under the group G , then $\rho_s(w) \in W$ and $\rho_s(w^0) \in W^0$. Therefore, $\rho_s(w)$ and $\rho_s(w^0)$ are projections of the vector $\rho_s(x)$ onto the subspaces W and W^0 . From this it follows that knowing the representations W and W^0 determine the representation V . In this case, the representation V is said to be the *direct sum* of the representations W and W^0 and denoted as follows: $V = W \oplus W^0$. Each element of the space V is identified with the pair (w, w^0) , where $w \in W$ and $w^0 \in W^0$. If the representations W and W^0 are given in matrix form R_s and R_s^0 , then the representation $W \oplus W^0$ is given by matrices of the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} R_s & 0 \\ 0 & R_s^0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The direct sum of any finite family of representations is defined similarly.

1.1.5 Irreducible representations

Let $\rho : G \rightarrow GL(V)$ be some linear representation of the group G . We say that it is *irreducible* or *simple* if V is not equal to 0 and has no G invariant subspaces, except 0 and V , of course. By theorem 1.1.2, this second condition is equivalent to the fact that V is not a *direct sum of two representations* (except for the trivial decomposition $V = 0 \oplus V$). Obviously, each representation of degree 1 is irreducible. In what follows we shall show that every non-commutative group has at least one irreducible representation of degree $n \geq 2$.

From irreducible representations using direct sums, you can make up any other representation.

Theorem 1.1.3 [*Maschke's Theorem*] *Each representation is a direct sum of irreducible representations.*

Proof: Let V be a linear representation of the group G . We proceed by induction on $\dim(V)$. If $\dim(V) = 0$, the theorem is obvious (0 direct sum of the empty family of irreducible representations). Suppose $\dim(V) \geq 1$. If V is irreducible, there is nothing to prove. Otherwise, by theorem 1.1.2, V can be expanded into a direct sum $V' \oplus V''$ with $\dim(V') < \dim(V)$ and $\dim(V'') < \dim(V)$. By inductive hypothesis, V' and V'' are direct sums of irreducible representations, and therefore the same applies to V . ■

Remark 1.1.4 *Let V be some representation and $V = W_1 \oplus \dots \oplus W_k$ its decomposition of V into a direct sum of irreducible representations. We can ask if this decomposition is unique? It is easy to see that in the case when all ρ_s are equal to 1, this decomposition, generally shows that, is not unique (in this case, all subspaces of W_i will be one-dimensional and the space V can be decomposed, of course, in various ways into the direct sum of one-dimensional subspaces). However, in Section 2.3 we will show that the number of representations of W_i isomorphic to a given irreducible representation of W does not depend on the choice of the decomposition.*

1.1.6 Tensor product of two representations

Along with the operation of a direct sum (which has the formal properties of an addition), one can define "multiplication" for representations - *tensor product*, sometimes called *Kronecker product*. It is defined as follows.

First of all, recall that the tensor product of two vector spaces V_1 and V_2 is a vector space W for which there exists a mapping $(x_1, x_2) \mapsto x_1 \cdot x_2$ of the direct product $V_1 \times V_2$ into W , satisfying the following two conditions:

- i. Mapping $(x_1, x_2) \mapsto x_1 \cdot x_2$ linearly in each of the variables x_1 and x_2 .
- ii. If (e_{i_1}) is some basis of the space V_1 , and (e_{i_2}) is some basis of the space V_2 , then the family of products $e_{i_1} \cdot e_{i_2}$ is the basis of the space W .

It is easy to see that such a space W exists and is unique (up to isomorphism); it is denoted by $V_1 \otimes V_2$. It follows from Condition (ii) that

$$\dim(V_1 \otimes V_2) = \dim V_1 \cdot \dim V_2.$$

Now let $\rho^1 : G \rightarrow GL(V_1)$ and $\rho^2 : G \rightarrow GL(V_2)$ be two linear representations of the group G . Assign to each element $s \in G$ an element ρ_s of the group $GL(V_1 \otimes V_2)$, satisfying the condition:

$$\rho_s(x_1 \cdot x_2) = \rho_s^1(x_1) \cdot \rho_s^2(x_2) \text{ for each } x_1 \in V_1, x_2 \in V_2.$$

The existence and uniqueness of the element ρ_s easily follows from conditions (i) and (ii). We will write in this case

$$\rho_s = \rho_s^1 \otimes \rho_s^2.$$

It is clear that ρ_s defines some linear representation of the group G in the space $V_1 \otimes V_2$, which is called the *tensor product* of the given representations ρ^1 and ρ^2 .

In the language of matrices, this definition looks like this: let (e_{i_1}) be the basis for V_1 , and let $r_{i_1 j_1}(s)$ be the matrix ρ_s^1 with respect to this basis and define (e_{i_2}) and $r_{i_2 j_2}(s)$ in the same way. Formulas:

$$\rho_s^1(e_{j_1}) = \sum_{i_1} r_{i_1 j_1}(s) \cdot e_{i_1}, \quad \rho_s^2(e_{j_2}) = \sum_{i_2} r_{i_2 j_2}(s) \cdot e_{i_2}$$

we get

$$\rho_s(e_{j_1} \cdot e_{j_2}) = \sum_{i_1, i_2} r_{i_1 j_1}(s) \cdot r_{i_2 j_2}(s) \cdot e_{i_1} \cdot e_{i_2}.$$

Accordingly, the linear transformation matrix of ρ_s has the form $(r_{i_1 j_1}(s)) \cdot (r_{i_2 j_2}(s))$, in which we recognize the *tensor product of matrices by an automorphism* ρ_s^1 and ρ_s^2 .

The tensor product of two irreducible representations is not, generally speaking, irreducible. It decomposes into a direct sum of irreducible representations that can be defined using character theory (cf. 2.3).

1.1.7 Linear representations of finite groups

A linear representation of the group G in a finite-dimensional Euclidean space E^n is a mapping f , by means of which each element a of this group is associated with a linear transformation T_a of the space E^n so that for any a_1 and a_2 from G the relation $T_{(a_1 a_2)} = T_{a_1} T_{a_2}$.

Thus, a linear representation of the group G in a finite-dimensional Euclidean space E^n is a homomorphism of this group onto some subset of linear transformations of this space.

In this paper, we are talking about a linear representations of finite groups and for this we consider the basic information about them and also some lemmas, namely the Schur lemma, which is the most interesting because it is one of the basic ones in the construction of the theory of representations of finite groups.

In mathematics, **Schur's lemma** is an elementary but extremely useful statement in the theory of representations of groups and algebras. In the group case it says that if M and N are finite-dimensional irreducible representations of some group G and ϕ is a linear transformation from M to N commuting with the action of the group, then either ϕ is a reversible isomorphism, or $\phi = 0$. An important special case takes place when $M = N$. The lemma is named after Isaiah Schur, who used it to prove orthogonality relations and to develop the foundations of the theory of representations of finite groups. Schur's lemma can be generalized to Lie groups and Lie algebras.

1.2 Character theory

1.2.1 The character of a representation

Let V be a vector space with a basis (e_i) of n elements, and let a be some linear mapping of V into itself, with a matrix (a_{ij}) . The *trace* of the mapping a is called the scalar

$$\text{Tr}(a) = \sum_i a_{ii}$$

It is known that the trace is equal to the *sum of eigenvalues* of the mapping a (calculated by x with their multiplicities), and does not depend on the choice of the basis (e_i) .

Now let $\rho : G \rightarrow GL(V)$ be some linear representation of the finite group G in the vector space V .

For each $s \in G$ we put:

$$\chi_\rho(s) = \text{Tr}(\rho_s)$$

The resulting complex function χ_ρ on the group G is called the *character* of the representation ρ . The importance of this function is determined by the fact that it characterizes the considered representation ρ (cf. 2.3).

Proposition 1.2.1 *Let χ be the character of some representation ρ of degree n , we have:*

1. $\chi(1) = n$;
2. $\chi(s^{-1}) = \chi(s)^*$ for any $s \in G$;
3. $\chi(tst^{-1}) = \chi(s)$ for any $s, t \in G$.

[If $z = x + iy$ is a complex number, then z^* denotes its complex conjugate $z^* = x - iy$.]

Proof: We have $\rho(1) = 1$ and $\text{Tr}(1) = n$, since V has dimension n , hence (1).

To prove statement (2), we see that each element of ρ_s has a finite order, therefore, all its eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n$ have the same property, and therefore they have an absolute value, equal to 1 (this is also a consequence of the fact that ρ_s can be defined using a unitary matrix, see section 1.4). Thus,

$$\chi(s)^* = \text{Tr}(\rho_s)^* = \sum \lambda_i^* = \sum \lambda_i^{-1} = \text{Tr}(\rho_s^{-1}) = \text{Tr}(\rho_{s^{-1}}) = \chi(s^{-1}).$$

Formula (3) can also be written as $\chi(vu) = \chi(uv)$, setting $u = ts$, $v = t^{-1}$. In this form, it follows from the well-known formula

$$\text{Tr}(ab) = \text{Tr}(ba)$$

valid for two arbitrary linear mappings a and b from V into itself. ■

Remark 1.2.2 A function f on the group G that satisfying identity (3), or which is the same condition $f(uv) = f(vu)$, is called a class function. In Section 2.5 we show that every class function is a linear combination of characters.

Proposition 1.2.3 Let $\rho^1 : G \rightarrow GL(V_1)$, $\rho^2 : G \rightarrow GL(V_2)$ be two linear representations of the group G , and let χ_1, χ_2 be their characters. Then:

(1) the character χ of the direct sum of the representations $V_1 \oplus V_2$ is equal to $\chi_1 + \chi_2$;

(2) The character ψ of the tensor product of the representations $V_1 \otimes V_2$ is equal to $\chi_1 \cdot \chi_2$.

Proof: We represent ρ^1 and ρ^2 in matrix form R_s^1 and R_s^2 . Then the representation of $V_1 \oplus V_2$ in mathematical form has the form

$$R_s = \begin{pmatrix} R_s^1 & 0 \\ 0 & R_s^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

whence $Tr(R_s) = Tr(R_s^1) + Tr(R_s^2)$, that is, $\chi(s) = \chi_1(s) + \chi_2(s)$.

Assertion (2) is proved similarly.

And we have

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_1(s) &= \sum_{i_1} r_{i_1 i_1}(s), & \chi_2(s) &= \sum_{i_2} r_{i_2 i_2}(s), \\ \psi(x) &= \sum_{i_1, i_2} r_{i_1 i_1}(s) r_{i_2 i_2}(s) = \chi_1(s) \cdot \chi_2(s). \end{aligned}$$

■

1.2.2 Schur's lemma - Basic Applications

Proposition 1.2.4 (Schur's lemma). Let $\rho^1 : G \rightarrow GL(V_1)$, $\rho^2 : G \rightarrow GL(V_2)$ be two irreducible representations of the group G , and let f be such a linear mapping of the space V_1 in V_2 such that $\rho_s^2 \circ f = f \circ \rho_s^1$ for all $s \in G$. Then:

1. If ρ^1 and ρ^2 are not isomorphic, we have $f = 0$.
2. If $V_1 = V_2$ and $\rho^1 = \rho^2$, then f is a homothety (that is, multiplication by some number).

Proof: The case $f = 0$ is trivial. Suppose now that $f \neq 0$ and let W_1 be its kernel (that is, the set of elements $x \in V_1$ such that $f(x) = 0$). For $x \in W_1$ we have $f \circ \rho_s^1(x) = \rho_s^2 \circ f(x) = 0$, whence $\rho_s^1(x) \in W_1$ and hence, the subspace W_1 is invariant under G . Since the representation ρ^1 is irreducible, then either

W_1 coincides with the entire space V_1 , or is equal to zero. The first case is excluded (it corresponds to $f = 0$). Therefore, $W_1 = 0$. In the same way, it is proved that the *image* W_2 of the mapping f (that is, the set of elements $f(x)$, for $x \in V_1$) coincides with the entire space V_2 . This implies that f is a *isomorphism* of the space V_1 onto the space V_2 , which proves assertion (1).

Suppose now that $V_1 = V_2$, $\rho^1 = \rho^2$ and let λ *eigenvalue* of the mapping f . There is at least one, since the field of scalars is a field of complex numbers. Put $f' = f - \lambda$. Since λ is an eigenvalue of f , the kernel of f' is nonzero. On the other hand, we have $\rho_s^2 \circ f' = f' \circ \rho_s^1$. The first part of the proof shows that these properties are possible only if $f' = 0$, that is, $f = \lambda$, as required. ■

We keep the assumption that V_1 and V_2 are irreducible and denote by g the *order* of the group G .

Corollary 1.2.5 *Let h be some linear mapping of the space V_1 into the space V_2 , and put:*

$$h^0 = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} (\rho_t^2)^{-1} h \rho_t^1.$$

Then

1. If ρ^1 and ρ^2 are not isomorphic, then $h^0 = 0$.
2. If V_1 and V_2 , $\rho^1 = \rho^2$, then h^0 is a homothety with the ratio factor $\frac{1}{n} \text{Tr}(h)$, where $n = \dim(V_1)$.

Proof: We have $\rho_s^2 \circ h^0 = h^0 \circ \rho_s^1$. Indeed:

$$(\rho_s^2)^{-1} h^0 \rho_s^1 = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} (\rho_s^2)^{-1} (\rho_t^2)^{-1} h \rho_t^1 \rho_s^1 = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} (\rho_{ts}^2)^{-1} h \rho_{ts}^1 = h^0.$$

Applying Proposition 1.2.4 to $f = h^0$, we see that in case (1) $h^0 = 0$, and in case (2) h^0 coincides with multiplication by the scalar λ . Moreover, in the latter case we have

$$\text{Tr}(h^0) = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \text{Tr}((\rho_t^1)^{-1} h \rho_t^1) = \text{Tr}(h),$$

and since $\text{Tr}(\lambda) = n\lambda$, we get $\lambda = \frac{1}{n} \text{Tr}(h)$. ■

Let us write down the result of the corollary 1.2.5 explicitly, assuming that the representations ρ^1 and ρ^2 are given in *matrix form*:

$$\rho_t^1 = (r_{i_1 j_1}(t)), \quad \rho_t^2 = (r_{i_2 j_2}(t)).$$

Let the linear mapping h be defined by the matrix $(x_{i_2 i_1})$, and also h^0 is defined by the matrix $(x_{i_2 i_1}^0)$. We have by definition of h^0 :

$$x_{i_2 i_1}^0 = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t, j_1, j_2} r_{i_2 j_2}(t^{-1}) x_{j_2 j_1} r_{j_1 i_1}(t).$$

The right side is linear form with respect to $x_{j_2 j_1}$. In case (1) this form vanishes for all systems of values $x_{j_2 j_1}$. Thus, all its coefficients are equal to zero. From this we obtain the assertion. Corollary.

Corollary 1.2.6 *In case (1), the equality*

$$\frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} r_{i_2 j_2}(t^{-1}) r_{j_1 i_1}(t) = 0$$

for all i_1, i_2, j_1, j_2 .

Similarly, in case (2), we similarly have $h^0 = \lambda$, that is, $x_{i_2 i_1}^0 = \lambda \delta_{i_2 i_1}$ (here $\delta_{i_2 i_1}$ denotes the Kronecker symbol is 1 if $i_1 = i_2$ and 0 otherwise) with $\lambda = \frac{1}{n} \text{Tr}(h)$, that is, which is the same, $\lambda = \frac{1}{n} \sum \delta_{j_2 j_1} x_{j_2 j_1}$. Hence we obtain the equality

$$\frac{1}{g} \sum_{t, j_1, j_2} r_{i_2 j_2}(t^{-1}) x_{j_2 j_1} r_{j_1 i_1}(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j_1, j_2} \delta_{i_2 i_1} \delta_{j_2 j_1} x_{j_2 j_1}.$$

Equating the coefficients for $x_{j_2 j_1}$, we get, as indicated above:

Corollary 1.2.7 *In case (2), the equality*

$$\frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} r_{i_2 j_2}(t^{-1}) r_{j_1 i_1}(t) = \frac{1}{n} \delta_{i_2 i_1} \delta_{j_2 j_1} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{n}, & \text{if } i_1 = i_2, j_1 = j_2, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Remark 1.2.8 1. *If φ and ψ are functions on G , then*

$$\langle \varphi, \psi \rangle = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \varphi(t^{-1}) \psi(t) = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \varphi(t) \psi(t^{-1}).$$

We have $\langle \varphi, \psi \rangle = \langle \psi, \varphi \rangle$. Moreover, $\langle \varphi, \psi \rangle$ is linear in φ and in ψ . With this notation, the corollaries 1.2.2 and 1.2.7 become, respectively

$$\langle r_{i_2 j_2}, r_{j_1 i_1} \rangle = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle r_{i_2 j_2}, r_{j_1 i_1} \rangle = \frac{1}{n} \delta_{i_2 i_1} \delta_{j_2 j_1}.$$

2. *Suppose that the matrices $(r_{i_2 j_2}(t))$ are unitary (this can always be achieved by a suitable choice of the basis (e_{i_2})). Then $r_{i_2 j_2}(t^{-1}) = r_{j_2 i_2}(t)^*$ and the corollaries 1.2.2 and 1.2.2 are orthogonality relations (with respect to the scalar product $(\varphi | \psi)$, which will be defined in the following section).*

1.2.3 Orthogonality relations for characters

Let's start with the notation. If ϕ and ψ are two complex-valued functions on the group G , we put

$$\langle \phi | \psi \rangle = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \phi(t)^* \psi(t)$$

where g is the order of the group G . The pairing $\langle \phi, \psi \rangle$ thus defined satisfies all the axioms of the *scalar product*: it is semilinear in ϕ , linear in ψ and $\langle \phi, \phi \rangle > 0$ for each function $\phi \neq 0$. It is called the *dot product of functions* defined on the group.

Remark 1.2.9 If $\check{\psi}$ is a function defined by the formula $\check{\psi}(t) = \psi(t^{-1})^*$, we have

$$(\phi | \psi) = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \phi(t) \check{\psi}(t^{-1}) = \langle \phi, \check{\psi} \rangle,$$

In particular, if χ is the character of the representation of the group G , we have $\check{\chi} = \chi$ (prop. 1.2.1), so $(\phi | \chi) = \langle \phi, \chi \rangle$ for all functions ϕ on G . So we can use $(\phi | \chi)$ or $\langle \phi, \chi \rangle$ at will.

Theorem 1.2.10 (1) If χ is a character of an irreducible representation, then we have $\langle \chi, \chi \rangle = 1$ (that is, χ has "length 1").

(2) If χ and χ' are characters of two non-isomorphic irreducible representations, then $\langle \chi, \chi' \rangle = 0$ (in other words, χ and χ' orthogonal).

Proof: Let $\rho : G \rightarrow GL(V)$ be an irreducible representation with character χ , and let n be its degree, then

$$\langle \chi, \chi \rangle = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \chi(t)^* \chi(t) = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \chi(t^{-1}) \chi(t)$$

(see proposal 1.2.1). If the representation ρ is given in the matrix form $\rho_t = (r_{ij}(t))$, then $\chi(t) = \sum_i r_{ii}(t)$, whence

$$\langle \chi, \chi \rangle = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t, i, j} r_{ii}(t^{-1}) r_{jj}(t).$$

Applying the corollary 1.2.7 of the proposition 1.2.4. we see that $\frac{1}{g} \sum_{t \in G} r_{ii}(t^{-1}) r_{jj}(t)$ is equal to 0 for $i \neq j$ and equals $\frac{1}{n}$ for $i = j$. But since the index i takes n values, we get from here that $\langle \chi, \chi \rangle = 1$.

Assertion (2) is proved similarly using corollary 1.2.2 in place of corollary 1.2.7. ■

At the same time, we can prove Theorem 1.2.10 in a different way:

(1) Let ρ be an irreducible representation with character χ , given in the matrix form $\rho_t = (r_{ij}(t))$. We have $\chi(t) = \sum r_{ii}(t)$, hence

$$(\chi | \chi) = \langle \chi, \chi \rangle = \sum_{i,j} \langle r_{ii}, r_{jj} \rangle.$$

But in accordance with the corollary 1.2.7 of the proposition 1.2.4 we have $\langle r_{ii}, r_{jj} \rangle = \frac{\delta_{ij}}{n}$, where n degree ρ . Thus

$$(\chi | \chi) = \left(\frac{\sum_{i,j} \delta_{ij}}{n} \right) = \frac{n}{n} = 1,$$

since the indices i, j each take n values.

(2) Let ρ be an irreducible representation with character χ and χ' , given in the matrix form $\rho_t = (r_{ij}(t))$. We have $\chi(t) = \sum r_{i_1 i_1}(t)$ and $\chi'(t) = \sum r_{j_1 j_1}(t)$, hence

$$(\chi | \chi') = \langle \chi, \chi' \rangle = \sum_{i,j} \langle r_{i_2 j_2}, r_{j_1 i_1} \rangle$$

But in accordance with the corollary 1.2.2 of the proposition 1.2.4 we have $\langle r_{i_2 j_2}, r_{j_1 i_1} \rangle = \frac{1}{n} \delta_{i_2 i_1} \delta_{j_2 j_1}$, where n is the degree ρ . Thus

$$(\chi | \chi') = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j_1, j_2} \delta_{i_2 i_1} \delta_{j_2 j_1} x_{j_2 j_1} x'_{j_2 j_1} = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{t, j_1 j_2} r_{i_2 j_2}(t^{-1}) x_{j_2 j_1} x'_{j_2 j_1} r_{j_1 i_1}(t) = 0$$

since the indices i, j each take n values.

Or

$$(\chi | \chi') = \langle \chi, \chi' \rangle = \sum_{i,j} \langle r_{i_2 j_2}, r_{j_1 i_1} \rangle = \sum_{i,j} 0 = 0$$

as noted 1.2.8.

Theorem 1.2.11 *Let V be a linear representation of the group G with character ϕ , and let V decompose into a direct sum of irreducible representations,*

$$V = W_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus W_k.$$

Then, if W is an irreducible representation with character χ , then the number of terms W_i isomorphic to the representation W is equal to the scalar product $(\phi | \chi) = \langle \phi, \chi \rangle$.

Proof: Let χ_i be the character of the representation W_i . Then, based on proposition 1.2.3, we have

$$\phi = \chi_1 + \cdots + \chi_k.$$

So $(\varphi | \chi) = (\chi_1 | \chi) + \cdots + (\chi_k | \chi)$. But, according to the previous theorem, $(\chi_i | \chi)$ is equal to 1 or 0, depending on whether W_i is isomorphic to the representation W or not. This proves the theorem. ■

Corollary 1.2.12 *The number of representations of W_i isomorphic to a given representation of W does not depend on the chosen decomposition.*

(This number is called "the number of times that W occurs in V representation", or "the number of times that W is contained in V ")

Proof: Indeed, the scalar product $(\varphi | \chi)$ does not obviously depend on the choice of the decomposition. ■

Remark 1.2.13 *In this sense, we can say that there is uniqueness in the decomposition of a representation into irreducible representations. We'll come back to this in Section 2.6.*

Corollary 1.2.14 *Two representations with the same character are isomorphic.*

Proof: Indeed, the corollary 1.2.12 shows that they contain the same number of times any given irreducible representation. ■

Previous results reduce the study of representations to the study of their characters. If $\chi_1, \dots, \chi_h$ are different irreducible characters of the group G , and if $W_1, \dots, W_h$ are the corresponding irreducible representations, then each representation of V is isomorphic to a direct sum of the form

$$V = m_1 W_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus m_h W_h,$$

where $m_i \geq 0$ are integers. In this case, the character ϕ of the representation V is equal to the sum $m_1 \chi_1 + \cdots + m_h \chi_h$, and we have $m_i = \langle \varphi, \chi_i \rangle$. [In particular, these considerations can be applied to the tensor product $W_i \otimes W_j$ of two irreducible representations W_i and W_j and show that the product $\chi_i \chi_j$ admits a decomposition of the form

$$\chi_i \chi_j = \sum_k m_{ij}^k \chi_k,$$

where all m_{ij}^k are integers greater than or equal to zero.] The orthogonality relations between χ_i imply, in addition, that

$$\langle \varphi, \varphi \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^h m_i^2.$$

Hence, we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 1.2.15 *If φ is a character of some representation V , then $(\varphi | \varphi)$ is an integer and we have $(\varphi | \varphi) = 1$ if and only if V is irreducible.*

Proof: Indeed, $\sum m_i^2$ is an integer that is equal to 1 if and only if one of m_i is equal to 1, and the rest are zero, that is, if V is isomorphic to one of W_i . ■

1.2.4 Decomposition of the regular representation

Notation. For the rest, we denote by $\chi_1, \dots, \chi_h$ the different characters of all irreducible representations of the group G and by $n_1, \dots, n_h$ their degrees, we have $n_i = \chi_i(1)$, (cf. 1.2.1).

Let R be a regular representation of the group G . Recall that it has a basis $(e_t)_{t \in G}$ such that $\rho_s(e_t) = e_{st}$. If $s \neq 1$, we have $st \neq t$ for all t , and this shows that the diagonal elements of the matrix ρ_s are equal to zero.

in particular, $Tr(\rho_s) = 0$. On the other hand, for $s = 1$, we have

$$Tr(\rho_s) = Tr(1) = \dim(R) = g.$$

this implies

Proposition 1.2.16 *The character ϕ of the regular representation is given by the formulas:*

$$\phi(1) = g \quad \text{where } g - \text{order of } G,$$

$$\phi(s) = 0, \quad \text{if } s \neq 1.$$

Corollary 1.2.17 *Each irreducible representation of W_i is contained in the regular representation with multiplicity equal to its degree n_i .*

Proof: by theorem 1.2.15, this number is equal to $\langle \phi, \chi_i \rangle$, and we have,

$$\langle \phi, \chi_i \rangle = \frac{1}{g} \sum_{s \in G} \phi(s) \chi_i(s) = \frac{1}{g} g \cdot \chi_i(1) = \chi_i(1) = n_i.$$

■

Corollary 1.2.18 (a) *The degrees of n_i satisfy the relation $\sum_{i=1}^h n_i^2 = g$.*

(b) *If $s \in G$ is different from 1, we have $\sum_{i=1}^h n_i \chi_i(s) = 0$.*

Proof: As a Corollary of 1.2.17, we have $\phi(s) = \sum n_i \chi_i(s)$, for all $s \in G$. Taking $s = 1$, we get (a), and $s \neq 1$ we get (b). ■

Remark 1.2.19 *The above result can be used to define irreducible representations of a given group G . Suppose that we have constructed several non-isomorphic irreducible representations of degrees $n_1, \dots, n_k$, in order for them to be all irreducible representations of the group G (up to isomorphism), it is necessary and sufficient that the condition $n_1^2 + \dots + n_k^2 = g$.*

1.2.5 Number of irreducible representations

Recall that a function f on a group G is called class function if $f(sts^{-1}) = f(s)$ for all $s, t \in G$.

Proposition 1.2.20 *Let f be a class function on the group G , and let $\rho : G \rightarrow GL(V)$ be some linear representation of the group G . Let ρ_f be a linear mapping of the space V into itself, defined as:*

$$\rho_f = \sum_{t \in G} f(t)\rho_t.$$

Then if the assignment V is irreducible and has character χ and degree n , then ρ_f is a homothety with the ratio λ given by:

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t \in G} f(t)\chi(t) = \frac{g}{n}(f | \chi^*).$$

Proof: We calculate $\rho_s^{-1}\rho_f\rho_s$, we have

$$\rho_s^{-1}\rho_f\rho_s = \sum_{t \in G} f(t)\rho_s^{-1}\rho_t\rho_s = \sum_{t \in G} f(t)\rho_{s^{-1}ts}.$$

If we put $u = s^{-1}ts$, then the equality can be rewritten as

$$\rho_s^{-1}\rho_f\rho_s = \sum_{u \in G} (sus^{-1})\rho_u = \sum_{u \in G} f(u)\rho_u = \rho_f.$$

Therefore, $\rho_f\rho_s = \rho_s\rho_f$. Then it follows from the second part of the proposition 1.2.4 that ρ_f is a homothety with some constant λ . The trace of such a homothety is obviously equal to $n\lambda$, and the trace ρ_f has the form

$$\sum_{t \in G} f(t)\text{Tr}(\rho_t) = \sum_{t \in G} f(t)\chi(t).$$

From here

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t \in G} f(t)\chi(t) = \frac{g}{n}(f | \chi^*),$$

Q.E.D. ■

Consider now the vector space H of all class functions on the group G . The characters $\chi_1, \dots, \chi_h$ of all different irreducible representations of the group G belong to H , as we know, to this space.

Theorem 1.2.21 *The characters $\chi_1, \dots, \chi_h$ constitute an orthonormal basis of the space H .*

Proof: By the theorem, 1.2.10, $\chi_1, \dots, \chi_h$ form an orthonormal system of functions in the space H . It remains to prove that they generate H , and for this it suffices to show that each element of H orthogonal to χ_i is equal to zero. Let f be such an element. For each representation $\rho : G \rightarrow GL(V)$ put $\rho_{f^*} = \sum_{t \in G} f(t)^* \rho_t$. Since the element f is orthogonal to all χ_i , then, according to the proposition 1.2.20, ρ_{f^*} is equal to zero in the case when the representation V is irreducible. Using the direct sum expansion, we make sure that it is equal to zero for an arbitrary representation. Applying this to the regular representation R and calculating the image of the basis vector e_1 with respect to the action ρ_{f^*} , we teach

$$\rho_{f^*}(e_1) = \sum_{t \in G} f(t)^* \rho_t(e_1) = \sum_{t \in G} f(t)^* e_t.$$

Since $\rho_{f^*} = 0$, then $f(t)^* = 0$ for all $t \in G$, whence $f = 0$. This completes the proof. ■

Recall that two elements t and t' of a group G are called *conjugate* if there is an element $s \in G$ such that $t' = sts^{-1}$. Conjugacy – is an equivalence relation that divides G into conjugate classes. (also called *conjugation classes*).

Theorem 1.2.22 *The number of irreducible representations of the group G (up to isomorphism) is equal to the number of conjugacy classes of elements of this group.*

Proof: Let $C_1, \dots, C_k$ be all different conjugacy classes of the group G . They say that the function f on the group G is central, it is obviously equivalent to the statement that it is constant on each class from $C_1, \dots, C_k$, thus, it is determined by a finite number of its values $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k$ which can be chosen quite arbitrarily. It follows from this that the dimension of the space H of all class functions on G is k . On the other hand, by Theorem 1.2.21, this dimension is equal to the number of irreducible representations of the group G (up to isomorphism). From here we get the desired result. ■

Let us immediately point out one more corollary of the theorem 1.2.22. Let $s \in G$, c_s the number of elements in the element class s and f_s a function equal to 1 on the element class s and 0 on the other classes. Since this function f_s is a class function,, then by theorem 1.2.22 we can represent it in the form

$$f_s = \sum_{i=1}^h x_i \chi_i,$$

where $x_i = \langle \chi_i, f_s \rangle = \frac{c_s}{g} \chi_i(s)^*$. Therefore, for each element $t \in G$ we have

$$f_s(t) = \frac{c_s}{g} \sum_{i=1}^h \chi_i(s)^* \chi_i(t).$$

Writing down, we get

$$\sum_{i=1}^h \chi_i(s)^* \chi_i(s) = \frac{g}{c_s}, \quad \text{if } t = s,$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^h \chi_i(s)^* \chi_i(t) = 0, \text{ if } s \text{ and } t \text{ are not conjugate.}$$

Example 1.2.23 For G we take the group of permutations of three letters. We have $g = 6$, and there are three classes: element 1, three transpositions, and two cyclic permutations. Let t be a transposition and c a cyclic permutation. We have $t^2 = 1, c^3 = 1, tc = c^2t$; whence there are only two characters of degree 1: the unit character χ_1 and the character χ_2 denoting sign permutations. Theorem 1.2.22 shows that there is another irreducible character θ ; if n is its degree, we must have $1 + 1 + n^2 = 6$, therefore, $n = 2$. The values of θ can be deduced from the fact that $\chi_1 + \chi_2 + 2\theta$ is the character of the regular representation of the group G (see proposition 1.2.16) Thus, we get the character table G

	1	t	c
χ_1	1	1	1
χ_2	1	-1	1
θ	2	0	-1

1.2.6 Canonical decomposition of a representation

Let $\rho : G \rightarrow GL(V)$ be a linear representation of the group G . We're going to define a direct sum decomposition of V , which is "coarser" than the decomposition into irreducible representations, but *uniquely defined*. This decomposition is obtained as follows:

Let, first of all, $\chi_1, \dots, \chi_h$ all different characters of the irreducible representations $W_1, \dots, W_h$ of the group G and $n_1, \dots, n_h$ their degrees. On the other hand, let $V = U_1 \oplus \dots \oplus U_m$ be some decomposition of V into a direct sum of irreducible representations. For each $i = 1, \dots, h$ denote by V_i the direct sum of those from $U_1, \dots, U_m$ which are isomorphic to W_i , it is obvious that:

$$V = V_1 \oplus \dots \oplus V_h.$$

(In other words, we have decomposed V into the direct sum of irreducible representations and *collected together* the isomorphic representations.)

This is the *canonical decomposition* we had in mind. It has the following properties:

Theorem 1.2.24 (a) *The decomposition of $V = V_1 \oplus \dots \oplus V_h$ does not depend on the initially chosen decomposition of V into irreducible representations.*

(b) *The projection p_i of the space V onto V_i associated with this decomposition is given by the formula:*

$$p_i = \frac{n_i}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \chi_i(t)^* \rho_t.$$

Proof: We will prove assertion (b). Statement (a) will follow because the projections p_i uniquely define V_i . We put

$$q_i = \frac{n_i}{g} \sum_{t \in G} \chi_i(t)^* \rho_t.$$

From Proposition 1.2.20 it follows that the restriction of q_i to the irreducible representation W with character χ and of degree n is a homothety with constant $\frac{n_i}{n}(\chi_i | \chi)$ so it is either 0 if $\chi \neq \chi_i$, or 1 if $\chi = \chi_i$. In other words, the mapping q_i is identical on the irreducible representation isomorphic to W_i , and zero on the others. By virtue of the definition of the representation V_i , it follows that the mapping q_i is identical on V_i and vanishes on all V_j for $j \neq i$. Let $x = x_1 + \cdots + x_h$ decompose an arbitrary element $x \in G$ into components $x_i \in V_i$, then, therefore,

$$q_i(x) = q_i(x_1) + \cdots + q_i(x_h) = x_i.$$

This means that q_i coincides with the projection p_i of the space V onto V_i , as required. $\blacksquare$

Thus, the decomposition of the representation V into irreducible representations can be done in two stages: first, determine the canonical decomposition $V = V_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus V_h$, this can be easily done using the formula, for projections p_i . Then, if necessary, decompose each V_i into a direct sum of irreducible representations, each of which is isomorphic to a representation of W_i :

$$V_i = W_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus W_i.$$

This last decomposition, as a rule, can be carried out, generally speaking, in an infinite number of ways. This is as arbitrary as choosing a basis in a vector space.

The following example illustrates this situation well. Take as G a group of two elements $\{1, s\}$ where $s^2 = 1$. This group has two irreducible representations of degree 1, W^+ and W^- , the corresponding mappings are $\rho_s = +1$ and $\rho_s = -1$. The canonical decomposition of an arbitrary representation V then has the form $V = V^+ \oplus V^-$ where the component V^+ (resp. V^-) consists of those elements $x \in V$ that are symmetric with respect to G ($\rho_s(x) = x$), and the component V^- is one of those that are antisymmetric ($\rho_s(x) = -x$). The corresponding projections are given by the formulas

$$p^+(x) = \frac{(x + \rho_s(x))}{2}, \quad p^-(x) = \frac{(x - \rho_s(x))}{2}.$$

In turn, decomposing the representations of V^+ and V^- into irreducible components is simply equivalent to decomposing them into a direct sum of *lines*.

Remark 1.2.25 (1) Let $x \in V_i$ and $V(x)$ be the subspace of the space V generated by the elements $\rho_s(x)$, $s \in G$. Obviously, $V(x)$ sub representation of V .

Its decomposition into irreducible representations includes the representations W_i a certain number of times (say, m times). The integer m (which depends on x) does not necessarily equal 1 (in other words, it is not always true that x is converted in the same way as W_i). One can only prove that m does not exceed the dimension n_i of the representation W_i .

(2) Let H_i be the vector space of linear mappings h of the space W_i into V_i (or into V , as you like) satisfying the condition $\rho_s h = h \rho_s$. Let us denote by $h_1, \dots, h_k$ the basis of this space and compose the direct sum $W_1 \oplus \dots \oplus W_k$ from k elements W_i . The system $(h_1, \dots, h_k)$ defines in an obvious way some linear mapping h of the space $W_1 \oplus \dots \oplus W_k$ into V_i . It can be shown that it is a (representation) isomorphism and that each isomorphism is obtained in this way. In other words, the decompositions of the representation V_i into the direct sum of irreducible representations (which is equivalent to specifying the isomorphism $W_1 \oplus \dots \oplus W_k \rightarrow V_i$) correspond to all possible choices of a basis in the vector space H_i .

Chapter 2

Irreducible representations of the symmetric group S_n over $\mathbb{C}$

Finite groups also have irreducible representations, and each finite-dimensional representation can be decomposed into a direct sum of a finite number of irreducible representations.

2.1 Symmetric group

The symmetric group plays an important role in some aspects of Lie theory. Therefore, we want to understand its irreducible representations. In this article, we will give a complete description of the irreducible representations of the symmetric group, that is, we will give the construction of irreducible representations using Young symmetrizers.

Symmetric group is the set of reversible transformations of the set of natural numbers $\{1, \dots, n\}$, where the group operation is the composition of transformations.

Definition 2.1.1 *The set of all permutations of the set X (i.e., bijections of $X \rightarrow X$) with the composition operation form a group which called the symmetric group or the permutation group of X .*

Usually denoted by $S(X)$. If $X = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, then $S(X)$ is denoted by S_n .

The composition of transformations is associative, there is a single element that is a trivial transformation, and for each transformation there is an inverse transformation, such that their composition is equal to the trivial transformation. In the case of $n \geq 3$, the group is non-abelian. The order of the group, that is, the number of its elements, is defined as

$$|S_n| = n!$$

There are several ways to describe an item in S_n .

Example 2.1.2 *The permutation $\sigma \in S_7$ can be written as*

$$\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 & 6 & 7 \\ 5 & 2 & 3 & 6 & 7 & 4 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\leftrightarrow \sigma = (157)(2)(3)(46) = (157)(46)$$

The last notation is the notation in terms of cycles, i.e. there is a cyclic permutation of elements inside each bracket. Cycles of length one, that is, cycles containing numbers on which the permutation acts trivially, are not counted.

Definition 2.1.3 *Representation of a finite group G on a finite-dimensional vector, the space V is a homomorphism from G to $GL(V) = \{A \in M_n(\mathbb{C}) : \det(A) \neq 0\}$.*

Definition 2.1.4 *A representation is irreducible if V does not have a proper nontrivial subspace invariant under the action of G .*

Proposition 2.1.5 *The number of irreducible representations of a finite group is equal to the number of conjugacy classes.*

Let G be an arbitrary group. If $g, x \in G$, we define that the element conjugate to g via x is xgx^{-1} . (Note: some texts define the conjugation of g with x as $x^{-1}gx$. By our definition, this would be the conjugation of g with x^{-1}). If $g, h \in G$ and there is some $x \in G$ such that $xgx^{-1} = h$, we say that g and h are conjugate in G . For a group G , we define the relation $\sim$ in terms of $g \sim h$ if g and h are conjugate in G .

Proposition 2.1.6 *Let G be a group, and define the relation $\sim$ on G as $g \sim h$ if g and h are conjugate in G . Then $\sim$ is an equivalence relation on G .*

Proof: We need to check that $\sim$ satisfies three defining properties of an equivalence relation. First, for any $g \in G$ we have $g \sim g$, since $ege^{-1} = g$, so the reflexivity property is satisfied. Now suppose $g \sim h$. Then there is some $x \in G$ such that $xgx^{-1} = h$. Then we get $g = x^{-1}hx$. Thus, we can conjugate h with x^{-1} to get g , so that $h \sim g$ and the reflexivity property is satisfied. Now suppose $g, h, k \in G$, where $g \sim h$ and $h \sim k$. Then there are $y, z \in G$ such that $gyg^{-1} = h$ and $zhz^{-1} = k$. Substituting the first expression for h into the second, we get $zygy^{-1}z^{-1} = k$, or $(zy)g(zy)^{-1} = k$. So we can conjugate g with zy to get k , so $g \sim k$ and the transitive property is satisfied. Thus, $\sim$ is an equivalence relation on G . ■

Since $\sim$ is an equivalence relation on G , its equivalence classes partition G . Equivalence classes in this respect are called conjugacy classes of the group G .

Proposition 2.1.7 *Let G be a group, and $x, g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n \in G$. Then, for any n , the element conjugated to $g_1g_2 \cdots g_n$ by x is the product of elements conjugated by x to the elements $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n$.*

Proposition 2.1.8 *Let G be a commutative group. Then, for any $a \in G$, the conjugacy class a is a one-element set $\{a\}$.*

Let us now define the conjugacy classes of the symmetric group S_n . We start by noticing that any conjugation of a k -cycle is again a k -cycle.

Recall the definition of a k -cycle:

Definition 2.1.9 *The substitution $\rho \in S_n$ is called a k -**cycle** if there is a natural number k and an integer $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that*

- (1) k is the smallest natural number such that $\rho^k(i) = i$,
- (2) ρ fixes every j not included in $\{i, \rho(i), \dots, \rho^{k-1}(i)\}$.

For example, if $X = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, a permutation $(1, 3, 2, 4)$ that sends 1 to 3, 3 to 2, 2 to 4 and 4 to 1, is a 4-cycle, and the permutation $(1, 3, 2)$, which sends 1 to 3, 3 to 2, 2 to 1 and 4 to 4, here 4 is a fixed element) is a 3-cycle.

Lemma 2.1.10 *Let $\alpha, \tau \in S_n$, where α - k - cycle $(a_1 a_2 \dots a_k)$. Then*

$$\tau \alpha \tau^{-1} = (\tau(a_1) \tau(a_2) \dots \tau(a_k)).$$

Proof: Consider $\tau(a_i)$ such that $1 \leq i \leq k$. Then $\tau^{-1} \tau(a_i) = a_i$ and $\alpha(a_i) = a_{i+1 \pmod k}$. Now we have $\tau \alpha \tau^{-1}(\tau(a_i)) = \tau(a_{i+1 \pmod k})$. Now take any j such that $j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$, but $j \neq a_i$ for any i . Then $\alpha(j) = j$, since j is not included in the k -cycle that defines α . So $\tau \alpha \tau^{-1}(\tau(j)) = \tau(j)$. Now we see that $\tau \alpha \tau^{-1}$ fixes any number that does not have the form $\tau(a_i)$ for some i , and we have

$$\tau \alpha \tau^{-1} = (\tau(a_1) \tau(a_2) \dots \tau(a_k)).$$

■

Theorem 2.1.11 *Any substitution in S_n decomposes into a product of independent cycles. These cycles are determined uniquely by substitution, up to their permutation.*

Proof: Indeed, suppose we have a substitution $\alpha \in S_n$. Let's see where 1 goes. If $1 \mapsto 1$, then this is a small cycle of length one. Let $i_1 \neq 1$, then look at $\alpha(i_1) = i_{i_1}$. If $i_{i_1} = 1$, then we got a cycle of length two. Let $i_{i_1} \neq 1$, then let's look at the image of this element, etc.

It is clear that at some moment the image of the next element will become equal to 1 (if the repetition happened on another element, then the mapping α would not be injective). This means that one cycle has appeared for us.

If this cycle does not sweep all the elements, then consider the next element in turn, which was not in the first cycle. A cycle is formed from it in the same way. The first and second cycles cannot intersect, since any intersection means that the map is not injective.

We will continue this procedure further, as a result of which we obtain a decomposition of the permutation into a product of disjoint cycles.

To understand that such a decomposition is unique, we only note that the partition of the set \$\{1, 2, \dots, n\}\$ of substitution elements into cycles is unambiguously, because only inside one cycle can one get from one element to another by rearranging the elements respectively \$\alpha\$ several times.

If we already know the set in one cycle, then the cycle itself is also formed unambiguously, since it is determined simply by the images of the elements. ■

We know by theorem 2.1.11 that for any permutation \$\alpha \in S_n\$ one can write \$\alpha\$ as a product of disjoint cycles. Suppose we write \$\alpha\$ this way and \$\alpha\$ has cycles of length \$k_1, k_2, k_3, \dots, k_\ell\$, where \$k_1 \ge k_2 \ge k_3 \ge \dots \ge k_\ell\$, and where we included units in this list for fixed points. We call the sequence \$(k_1, k_2, k_3, \dots, k_\ell)\$ the cyclic type \$\alpha\$. Note that \$\sum_{i=1}^\ell k_i = n\$, since every element in \$\{1, 2, \dots, n\}\$ is either fixed or appears in some kind of cycle.

Example 2.1.12 *If \$\sigma \in S_{10}\$ and \$\sigma = (1345)(2789)\$, then \$\sigma\$ is of cyclic type \$(4, 4, 1, 1)\$.*

We can now describe the conjugacy classes of symmetric groups.

Theorem 2.1.13 *The conjugation classes in the \$S_n\$ group are determined by the cycle type. That is, if \$\sigma\$ is of cyclic type \$(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_\ell)\$, then any conjugation \$\rho\$ has cyclic type \$(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_\ell)\$, and if \$\tau\$ is any other element from \$S_n\$ with cyclic type \$(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_\ell)\$, then \$\sigma\$ is conjugate to \$\tau\$.*

Proof: Suppose \$\sigma\$ is of cyclic type \$(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_\ell)\$, so \$\sigma\$ can be written as a product of disjoint cycles as \$\sigma = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_\ell\$, where \$\alpha_i\$ is the \$k_i\$-cycle. Let \$\tau \in S_n\$, then by proposition 2.1.7 we have

$$(2.1) \quad \tau \sigma \tau^{-1} = \tau (\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_\ell) \tau^{-1} = (\tau \alpha_1 \tau^{-1}) (\tau \alpha_2 \tau^{-1}) \dots (\tau \alpha_\ell \tau^{-1}).$$

Now, for every \$i\$ such that \$1 \le i \le \ell\$, \$\alpha_i\$ is a \$k_i\$-cycle. From lemma 2.1.10 we know that \$\tau \alpha_i \tau^{-1}\$ is also a \$k_i\$-cycle. For any \$i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, \ell\}\$ such that \$i \neq j\$, we know that \$\alpha_i\$ and \$\alpha_j\$ are disjoint, and therefore \$\tau \alpha_i \tau^{-1}\$ and \$\tau \alpha_j \tau^{-1}\$ must be disjoint, since \$\tau\$ is a one-to-one function. So, the product in (2.1) above is \$\tau \sigma \tau^{-1}\$, written as a product of disjoint cycles, and \$\tau \alpha_i \tau^{-1}\$ is \$k_i\$-cycle. Now we see that any conjugation \$\rho\$ is of cyclic type \$(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_\ell)\$.

Now let \$\sigma, \rho \in S_n\$ be of cyclic type \$(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_\ell)\$, and we will show that \$\sigma\$ and \$\rho\$ are conjugate in \$S_n\$. Let \$\sigma\$ and \$\tau\$ be written as products disjoint cycles in the form

$$\sigma = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_\ell \quad \text{and} \quad \rho = \beta_1 \beta_2 \dots \beta_\ell,$$

where \$\alpha_i\$ and \$\beta_i\$ are \$k_i\$-cycles. For each \$i\$ we write

$$\alpha_i = (a_{i1} a_{i2} \dots a_{i k_i}) \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_i = (b_{i1} b_{i2} \dots b_{i k_i}).$$

Now we define \$\tau\$ as \$\tau(a_{ij}) = b_{ij}\$ for any \$i, j\$ such that \$1 \le i \le \ell\$ and \$1 \le j \le k_i\$. By Lemma 2.1.10 we have \$\tau \alpha_i \tau^{-1} = \beta_i\$. So, from proposition 2.1.7 we have

$$\tau\sigma\tau^{-1} = (\tau\alpha_1\tau^{-1})(\tau\alpha_2\tau^{-1})\cdots(\tau\alpha_\ell\tau^{-1}) = \beta_1\beta_2\cdots\beta_\ell = \rho.$$

So, any two elements of S_n with the same cycle type belong to the same conjugacy class. ■

Since two permutations are conjugate if and only if they have the same cyclic decomposition, the conjugacy class of the symmetric group S_n is marked by the cyclic decomposition of its elements. We denote the conjugacy class of the symmetric group S_n by C_i , where $i = (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n)$ is a multi-index such that i_j is equal to the number of cycles of length j .

For the example 2.1.2 $\sigma = (157)(46) \in S_7$ the corresponding multi-index is $i = (2, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0)$. From these notation we can find the partition n for natural numbers

$$n = \sum_{j=0}^n j \cdot i_j$$

for example for the above example $7 = 2 \cdot 1 + 2 + 3 = 1 + 1 + 2 + 3$.

According to Theorem 2.1.13, the partitions n are in one-to-one correspondence with the conjugacy classes S_n . The number of partitions of a positive number n is denoted by $p(n)$. Thus, $p(n)$ is equal to the number of conjugacy classes S_n .

Recall the definitions of transposition and permutation sign:

Definition 2.1.14 *Transposition is a 2-cycle.*

Definition 2.1.15 *A permutation is considered even if it can be written as the product of an even number of transpositions, and odd if it can be written as an odd number of transpositions.*

For example, the identity permutation $id = (1, 2)(1, 2)$, is therefore even. This follows directly from the definition that an even permutation multiplied by another even permutation is even, an even permutation multiplied by an odd is odd, an odd multiplied by an even is odd, and an odd multiplied by an odd is even.

However, it is not clear if the permutation can be odd and even at the same time.

Theorem 2.1.16 *Each permutation is either odd or even, but not both at the same time.*

Proof: First, we know from the previous proposition that each permutation can be written as a product of transpositions, so the only problem is to prove that it is impossible to find two expressions for a given permutation, one using the product $s_1s_2\cdots s_{2m+1}$ of an odd number of transpositions and one using the product $t_1t_2\cdots t_{2l}$ of an even number of transpositions. The steps are as follows:

- If this were the case, then we would have $id = t_{2l} \cdots t_1 s_1 \cdots s_{2m+1}$, the expression of identity as the result of an odd number of transpositions, so it suffices to prove that this is impossible.

- Note that any transposition of (i, j) can be written

$$(j-1, j) \cdots (i+2, i+3)(i+1, i+2) \times (i, i+1) \times (i+1, i+2)(i+2, i+3) \cdots (j-1, j)$$

where we have assumed without loss of generality that $i < j$. This is the result of an odd number of adjacent transpositions, that is, transpositions of the form $(k, k + 1)$.

- Thus, it suffices to show that identity cannot be written as the product of an odd number of adjacent transpositions.

- Consider polynomials in n variables $x_1, \dots, x_n$. If you have a polynomial like this $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and a permutation $\sigma \in S_n$, you get a new polynomial $\sigma(f)$ by replacing each x_i in f with $x_{\sigma(i)}$. For example, if $\sigma = (1, 2, 3)$ and $f = x_1 + x_2^2$ then $\sigma(f) = x_2 + x_3^2$. Define

$$A = \prod_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} (x_i - x_j).$$

- Note that for any $k, (k, k + 1)(A) = -A$, and therefore any product of an odd number of adjacent transpositions sends A to $-A$ too.

- We obtain a contradiction from the fact that $id(A) = A$. ■

Identical permutation is an even permutation. [1] An even permutation can be obtained as a composition of an even number and only an even number of exchanges (called transpositions) of two elements, while an odd permutation can be obtained by (only) an odd number of transpositions. [Nathan Jacobson. Basic algebra II. (2nd ed.). - New York: Dover Publications, 2009 .- 703 p.]

Definition 2.1.17 *The permutation sign σ , written $sign(\sigma)$, is*

$$sign(\sigma) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{where } \sigma \text{ even,} \\ -1, & \text{where } \sigma \text{ odd.} \end{cases}$$

So $sign(a_0, \dots, a_{m-1}) = (-1)^{m-1}$. The sign has a nice property:

Proposition 2.1.18 *For any permutations σ and τ we have $sign(\sigma\tau) = sign(\sigma)sign(\tau)$.*

Proof: It is simply a repetition of the fact that an even permutation composed with an even permutation is even, an odd permutation composed with an odd permutation is even, and an odd permutation composed with an even permutation is odd. ■

This allows us to find the sign of an arbitrary permutation: first express it as a product of cycles (they should not be disjoint), then use this result and the fact that cycles of even length are odd, and cycles of odd length are even.

Example 2.1.19 Since S_n has at least three conjugacy classes, it has at least three irreducible representations:

One is called a **trivial representation**, which is defined over $\mathbb{C}$ and acts by the formula $\sigma(v) = v$ for $\sigma \in S_n$ and $v \in \mathbb{C}$.

The other is called **alternate representation**, which is also over $\mathbb{C}$, but acts as $\sigma(v) = \text{sign}(\sigma)v$ for $\sigma \in S_n$ and $v \in \mathbb{C}$.

The third irreducible representation of S_n is called the **standard representation**, and it is located on $V = \{(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \in \mathbb{C}^n : z_1 + z_2 + \dots + z_n = 0\}$, acting through $\sigma((z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n)) = (z\sigma(1), z\sigma(2), \dots, z\sigma(n))$ for $\sigma \in S_n$ and $(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \in \mathbb{C}^n$.

Note that there are more irreducible representations for $n > 3$ than just these three.

Positive integer splitting n , also called integer splitting, is a way of writing n as the sum of positive integers. Two sums differing only in the order of the terms are considered to be the same partition. (If order matters, the sum becomes composition.)

For example, 5 can be split in 7 different ways:

- 5
- 4 + 1
- 3 + 2
- 3 + 1 + 1
- 2 + 2 + 1
- 2 + 1 + 1 + 1
- 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1

The order-dependent composition 1 + 3 is the same partition as 3 + 1.

The term in the partition is also called a part. The number of partitions n is determined by the statistical sum $p(n)$. Thus, $p(5) = 7$. The notation $\lambda \vdash n$ means that λ is a partition of the number n .

The table for $p(n)$ ($n \leq 100$) can be found in the book [G. E. Andrews. The theory of partitions. 1976. 266 p.]

In some sources, partitions are interpreted as a sequence of terms, rather than as an expression with a plus sign. For example, partition 2 + 2 + 1 could instead be written as a tuple (2, 2, 1) or in an even more compact form $(2^2, 1)$, where the superscript indicates the number of times the term is repeated.

Definition 2.1.20 Partition λ of the number n is the representation of the number n in the form $n = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \dots + \lambda_p$, where λ_i are natural numbers and $\lambda_i \geq \lambda_{i+1}$.

Proposition 2.1.21 Conjugacy classes S_n correspond to partitions of n .

Proof: The Conjugacy classes S_n are uniquely identified by the cyclic type of their members, and each class contains only one type of cycle. Thus, conjugacy classes correspond to partitioning n into a cyclic class type. ■

In general, the number of conjugacy classes in the symmetric group S_n is equal to the number of integer partitions n . This is because each conjugacy class corresponds to exactly one partition of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ into cycles up to permutation of elements $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

In fact, for S_n , irreducible representations are in a natural way in bijective correspondence with conjugacy classes; we will demonstrate this correspondence in the remainder of this section. **Young diagrams** are a fundamental tool for tracking combinatorial data associated with partitions, and are especially important for the theory of representations of symmetric groups. To this λ we attach the Young diagram Y_λ , which is the union of the rectangles $-i \leq y \leq i + 1, 0 \leq x \leq \lambda_i$ in the coordinate plane for $i = 1, \dots, p$. It is clear that Y_λ is a collection of n unit squares. **Young's table** corresponding to Y_λ is the result of filling the squares Y_λ with numbers $1, \dots, n$ in some way (no repetitions). For example, we will consider Young's table T_λ , obtained by filling in numbers in ascending order from left to right, top to bottom.

For example, the Young diagram for the partition $\mu = (3, 3, 2, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$ has the following form:

1	2	3
4	5	6
7	8	
9		

Details of the 0 size do not appear on the Young diagram. To refer to specific blocks in a Young diagram, fields are numbered from 1 to n in reading order.

Example 2.1.22 For S_3 ,

1	2	3
---	---	---

 is a Young diagram of $(3, 0, 0)$ partition,

1
2
3

 is a Young diagram of the $(1, 1, 1)$ partition and

1	2
3	

 is a Young diagram of the $(2, 1, 0)$ partition.

We can define two subgroups in S_n corresponding to T_λ :

1. Row subgroup P_λ : a subgroup that maps each element in $\{1, \dots, n\}$ to an element on the same row in T_λ .
2. Column Subgroup Q_λ : A subgroup that maps each element in $\{1, \dots, n\}$ to an element in the same column in T_λ .

It is clear that $P_\lambda \cap Q_\lambda = \{1\}$.

Let $P_\lambda = \{g \in S_n : g \text{ preserve every row}\}$ and let $Q_\lambda = \{g \in S_n : g \text{ preserve every column}\}$. For example, if $\mu = (3, 3, 2, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$, $(13) \in P_\mu$, because 1 and 3 are both in the first row, but $(13) \notin Q_\mu$ because 1 is in the first column and 3 is in the third column, thus swapping the columns of those two numbers.

Example 2.1.23 For Young diagram $\lambda = \begin{array}{|c|c|c|} \hline 1 & 2 & 3 \\ \hline \end{array}$ each permutation preserves rows. Thus, $P_{(3,0,0)} = P_\lambda = S_n = \{1, (12), (13), (23), (123), (321)\}$. However, only identity preserves the columns, so $Q_{(3,0,0)} = Q_\lambda = \{1\}$.

For Young diagram $\mu = \begin{array}{|c|} \hline 1 \\ \hline 2 \\ \hline 3 \\ \hline \end{array}$ only identity preserves rows, so $P_\lambda = P_{(1,1,1)} = \{1\}$. On the other hand, each permutation preserves a column, so $Q_\lambda = Q_{(1,1,1)} = S_n = \{1, (12), (13), (23), (123), (321)\}$.

For Young diagram $\lambda = \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline 1 & 2 \\ \hline 3 & \\ \hline \end{array}$ only identity and (12) preserve rows, so $P_\lambda = P_{(2,1,0)} = \{1, (12)\}$. The identity and (13) preserve the column, therefore $Q_\lambda = Q_{(2,1,0)} = \{1, (13)\}$.

To use P_λ and Q_λ to define irreducible representations of S_n , it is important to know the space of those representations. For this purpose, let $\mathbb{C}S_n$ be the group algebra S_n , that is, a vector space with base $\{e_g : g \in S_n\}$ with multiplication given by $e_g \cdot e_h = e_{gh}$. $\mathbb{C}S_n$ is a part of the vector space used to construct irreducible representations from P_λ and Q_λ .

For partition λ , define **Young's projectors**

$$a_\lambda := \frac{1}{|P_\lambda|} \sum_{g \in P_\lambda} e_g,$$

$$b_\lambda := \frac{1}{|Q_\lambda|} \sum_{g \in Q_\lambda} (-1)^g e_g$$

where $(-1)^g$ denotes the sign of the permutation g .

Example 2.1.24 The values of P_λ and Q_λ for Young diagrams S_3 are: $P_{(3,0,0)} = \{1, (12), (13), (23), (123), (321)\}$, so $a_{(3,0,0)} = e_1 + e_{(12)} + e_{(13)} + e_{(23)} + e_{(123)} + e_{(321)}$. $Q_{(3,0,0)} = \{1\}$, so $b_{(3,0,0)} = e_1$. $P_{(1,1,1)} = \{1\}$, therefore $a_{(1,1,1)} = e_1$. $Q_{(1,1,1)} = \{1, (12), (13), (23), (123), (321)\}$, therefore $b_{(1,1,1)} = e_1 - e_{(12)} - e_{(13)} - e_{(23)} + e_{(321)} + e_{(123)}$. $P_{(2,1,0)} = \{1, (12)\}$, therefore $a_{(2,1,0)} = e_1 + e_{(12)}$. $Q_{(2,1,0)} = \{1, (13)\}$, therefore $b_{(2,1,0)} = e_1 - e_{(13)}$.

Definition 2.1.25 Young Symmetrizer c_λ for partitioning λ is defined as $c_\lambda = b_\lambda \cdot a_\lambda$, sometimes $c_\lambda = a_\lambda \cdot b_\lambda$.

Since $P_\lambda \cap Q_\lambda = \{1\}$, the Young's symmetrizer element is nonzero.

Example 2.1.26 Young symmetrizers of the Young diagrams S_3 are: $c_{(3,0,0)} = a_{(3,0,0)}b_{(3,0,0)} = (e_1 + e_{(12)} + e_{(13)} + e_{(23)} + e_{(321)} + e_{(123)})e_1 = e_1 + e_{(12)} + e_{(13)} +$

$$e_{(23)} + e_{(321)} + e_{(123)}.$$

Similarly $c_{(1,1,1)} = a_{(1,1,1)}b_{(1,1,1)} = e_1(e_1 - e_{(12)} - e_{(13)} - e_{(23)} + e_{(321)} + e_{(123)}) = e_1 - e_{(12)} - e_{(13)} - e_{(23)} + e_{(321)} + e_{(123)}.$

For $(2, 1, 0)$, $c_{(2,1,0)} = a_{(2,1,0)}b_{(2,1,0)} = (e_1 + e_{(12)})(e_1 - e_{(13)}) = e_1 + e_{(12)} - e_{(13)} - e_{(123)}.$

The irreducible representations of S_n are described by the following theorem.

Theorem 2.1.27 *The subspace $V_\lambda := \mathbb{C}[S_n]c_\lambda$ of $\mathbb{C}[S_n]$ is an irreducible representation of S_n under left multiplication. Every irreducible representation of S_n is isomorphic to V_λ for a unique λ .*

The V_λ modules are called **Specht modules**.
 The proof of this theorem is given in the next subsection.

2.2 Proof of the classification theorem for representations of S_n

Lemma 2.2.1 *Let $\ell : \mathbb{C}[S_n] \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, where $\mathbb{C}$ is the linear function given by the formula*

$$\ell(\sigma) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \sigma \notin P_\lambda Q_\lambda \\ \text{sign}(q) & \text{if } \sigma = pq, \text{ where } p \in P_\lambda \text{ and } q \in Q_\lambda. \end{cases}$$

Then for any $x \in \mathbb{C}[S_n]$ we have

$$a_\lambda x b_\lambda = \ell(x) a_\lambda b_\lambda = \ell(x) c_\lambda$$

Proof: If $g \in P_\lambda Q_\lambda$, then g has a unique representation in the form pq , $p \in P_\lambda$, $q \in Q_\lambda$, therefore $a_\lambda g b_\lambda = (-1)^q c_\lambda$. Thus, to prove the required statement, we need to show that if g is a permutation not included in $P_\lambda Q_\lambda$, then $a_\lambda g b_\lambda = 0$.

To show this, it is enough to find a transposition t such that $t \in P_\lambda$ and $g^{-1}tg \in Q_\lambda$; then

$$a_\lambda g b_\lambda = a_\lambda t g b_\lambda = a_\lambda g (g^{-1}tg) b_\lambda = -a_\lambda g b_\lambda,$$

so $a_\lambda g b_\lambda = 0$. In other words, we have to find two elements i, j , standing in the same row of the table $T = T_\lambda$ and in the same column in the table $T' = gT$ (where gT is a table of the same form as and table T obtained by permutation

of elements of table T by permutation g). Thus, it suffices to show that if such a pair does not exist, then $g \in P_\lambda Q_\lambda$, i.e., there exists $p \in P_\lambda, q \in Q_\lambda := gQ_\lambda g^{-1}$ such that $pT = q'T'$ (so that $g = pq^{-1}, q = g^{-1}q'g \in Q_\lambda$).

Any two elements in the first row of T must be in different columns of T' , so there is $q'_1 \in Q_\lambda$ that moves all those elements to the first row. Hence, there is $p_1 \in P_\lambda$ such that p_1T and q'_1T have the same first row. Now follow the same procedure with the second line, finding the elements p_2, q'_2 such that p_2p_1T and $q'_2q'_1T$ have the same first two rows. Continuing this way, we construct the required elements p, q' . The lemma is proved. $\blacksquare$

We introduce **lexicographic ordering** on partitions: $\lambda > \mu$, if the first nonvanishing $\lambda_i - \mu_i$ is positive.

Lemma 2.2.2 *Let $\lambda, \mu \in S_n$, and choose the corresponding Young tables T_λ and T_μ . If $\lambda > \mu$, then $a_\lambda \mathbb{C}[S_n] b_\mu = 0$.*

Proof: As in the previous lemma, it suffices to show that for any $g \in S_n$ there exists a transposition $t \in P_\lambda$ such that $g^{-1}tg \in Q_\mu$. Let $T = T_\lambda$ and $T' = gT_\mu$. We are claiming that there are two integers that are in one row T and one column T' . Indeed, if $\lambda_1 > \mu_1$, this is clear from the cell principle (already for the first row). Otherwise, if $\lambda_1 = \mu_1$, as in the proof of the previous lemma, we can find elements $p_1 \in P_\lambda, q'_1 \in gQ_\mu g^{-1}$ such that p_1T and q'_1T' have the same first row, and repeat the reasoning for the second row, and so on. In the end, making $i - 1$ of such steps, we get $\lambda_i > \mu_i$, which means that some two elements of the i th row of the first table are in the same column of the second table, completing the proof. $\blacksquare$

Lemma 2.2.3 *c_λ is proportional to idempotent. Namely $c_\lambda^2 = \frac{n!}{\dim V_\lambda} c_\lambda$.*

Proof: According to lemma 2.2.1 we have

$$c_\lambda^2 = a_\lambda(b_\lambda a_\lambda)b_\lambda = \ell(b_\lambda a_\lambda)c_\lambda.$$

Let $\alpha = c(b_\lambda a_\lambda) \in \mathbb{C}$, and let $u - \mathbb{C}$ be a linear endomorphism $\mathbb{C}[S_n]$, given by right multiplication by c_λ . According to the above calculation, $u^2 = \alpha u$, so all eigenvalues of u are in $\{0, \alpha\}$, therefore

$$\text{Tr}(u) = \alpha \text{rk}(u) = \alpha \dim(V_\lambda).$$

On the other hand,

$$c_\lambda = 1 + \sum_{\sigma \in P_\lambda Q_\lambda - \{1\}} \pm \sigma$$

thus, using the basis $\mathbb{C}[S_n]$ given by S_n , we see that $\text{Tr}(c_\lambda) = n!$, therefore $\alpha = \frac{n!}{\dim(V_\lambda)}$. $\blacksquare$

Lemma 2.2.4 *Let A be an algebra and e an idempotent in A . Then, for any left A -module M , $\text{Hom}_A(Ae, M) \simeq eM$ holds (namely, $x \in eM$ corresponds to $f_x : Ae \rightarrow M$ given by the formula $f_x(a) = ax, a \in Ae$).*

Proof: Note that $1 - e$ is also an idempotent in A . Thus, the statement follows from the fact that $\text{Hom}_A(A, M) \simeq M$ and decomposition $A = Ae \oplus A(1 - e)$. ■

We are now ready to prove Theorem 2.1.27. Let $\lambda \geq \mu$. Then, by lemma 2.2.3 and 2.2.4.

$$\text{Hom}_{S_n}(V_\lambda, V_\mu) = \text{Hom}_{S_n}(\mathbb{C}[S_n]c_\lambda, \mathbb{C}[S_n]c_\mu) = c_\lambda \mathbb{C}[S_n]c_\mu.$$

The last space is equal to zero for $\lambda > \mu$ by lemma 2.2.2. and one-dimensional if $\lambda = \mu$ by lemmas 2.2.1 and 2.2.3. Therefore, V_λ are irreducible and V_λ is not isomorphic to V_μ if $\lambda \neq \mu$. Since the number of partitions is equal to the number of conjugacy classes in S_n , the representations of V_λ exhaust all the irreducible representations of S_n . The theorem is proved.

Example 2.2.5 *In this example, the irreducible representations of S_3 will be obtained in accordance with the theory introduced above. Since S_3 contains three conjugacy classes, three irreducible representations will be found. First, define the conjugacy classes S_3 that should identify the partitions of $n = 3$ into positive integers:*

- 3
- 2 + 1
- 1 + 1 + 1

Then we draw the corresponding Young diagrams.

- $\lambda = (3)$:

- $\lambda = (2, 1)$:

- $\lambda = (1, 1, 1)$:

Now we fill to find the standard Young tables for each contingency class.

- $\lambda = (3)$:

- $\lambda = (2, 1)$:

$$\begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline 1 & 2 \\ \hline 3 & \\ \hline \end{array} \quad \text{or} \quad \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline 1 & 3 \\ \hline 2 & \\ \hline \end{array}$$

- $\lambda = (1, 1, 1)$:

$$\begin{array}{|c|} \hline 1 \\ \hline 2 \\ \hline 3 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

For the partition $\lambda = (2, 1)$, two different standard Young tables are found. In fact, the irreducible representation obtained from some Young diagram does not depend on the filling. This will become clear when calculating the nature of the irreducible representation, which will depend only on the conjugacy class of the symmetric group, i.e. from Young's diagram, but not from filling.

The next step is to define two subgroups in S_3 for each Young table and introduce the corresponding elements in group algebra.

- $\lambda = (3)$:

$$P_{(3)} = S_3 \quad , \quad Q_{(3)} = \{1\}$$

$$a_{(3)} = \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} e_{\sigma} \quad , \quad b_{(3)} = e_1$$

- $\lambda = (2, 1)$, to select the canonical Young table:

$$P_{(2,1)} = \{1, (12)\} \quad , \quad Q_{(2,1)} = \{1, (13)\}$$

$$a_{(2,1)} = e_1 + e_{(12)} \quad , \quad b_{(2,1)} = e_1 - e_{(13)}$$

- $\lambda = (1, 1, 1)$:

$$P_{(1,1,1)} = \{1\} \quad , \quad Q_{(1,1,1)} = S_3$$

$$a_{(1,1,1)} = e_1 \quad , \quad b_{(1,1,1)} = \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma) e_{\sigma}.$$

We define Young's symmetrizers and obtain an irreducible representation V_{λ} for each partition λ according to the theorem 2.1.27.

- $\lambda = (3)$:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{(3)} &= a_{(3)} \cdot b_{(3)} = \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} e_\sigma \rightarrow V_{(3)} = \mathbb{C}S_3 \cdot c_{(3)} = \mathbb{C}\{e_\tau : \tau \in S_3\} \cdot \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} e_\sigma = \\ &= \mathbb{C} \left\{ \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} e_{\tau\sigma} : \tau \in S_3 \right\} = \mathbb{C} \left\{ \sum_{\sigma' \in S_3} e_{\sigma'} : \tau \in S_3 \right\} = \mathbb{C} \sum_{\sigma' \in S_3} e_{\sigma'} \end{aligned}$$

This is a trivial representation, since any $\tau \in S_3$ acts trivially on $V_{(3)}$:

- $\lambda = (2, 1)$:

$$c_{(2,1)} = (e_1 + e_{(12)}) \cdot (e_1 - e_{(13)}) = e_1 + e_{(12)} - e_{(13)} - e_{(132)}$$

$$\rightarrow V_{(2,1)} = \mathbb{C}S_3 \cdot c_{(2,1)}$$

Young's symmetrizer acts on each basis vector of group algebra by right multiplication:

$$e_1 \cdot c_{(2,1)} = c_{(2,1)}$$

$$e_{(12)} \cdot c_{(2,1)} = e_{(12)1} + e_{(12)(12)} - e_{(12)(13)} - e_{(12)(132)} = e_{(12)} + e_1 - e_{(132)} - e_{(13)} = c_{(2,1)}$$

$$e_{(13)} \cdot c_{(2,1)} = e_{(13)} + e_{(123)} - e_1 - e_{(12)}$$

$$e_{(23)} \cdot c_{(2,1)} = e_{(23)} + e_{(132)} - e_{(123)} - e_{(12)}$$

$$e_{(123)} \cdot c_{(2,1)} = e_{(123)} + e_{(13)} - e_{(23)} - e_1 = e_{(13)} \cdot c_{(2,1)}$$

$$e_{(132)} \cdot c_{(2,1)} = e_{(132)} + e_{(23)} - e_{(12)} - e_{(123)} = e_{(23)} \cdot c_{(2,1)}$$

$$\rightarrow V_{(2,1)} = \mathbb{C}\{c_{(2,1)}, e_{(13)} \cdot c_{(2,1)}, e_{(23)} \cdot c_{(2,1)}\} = \mathbb{C}\{c_{(2,1)}, e_{(23)} \cdot c_{(2,1)}\}$$

$$\text{since } c_{(2,1)} + e_{(23)} \cdot c_{(2,1)} = -e_{(13)} \cdot c_{(2,1)},$$

that is, $V_{(2,1)}$ is a two-dimensional irreducible representation of S_3 . This irreducible representation is often referred to as the standard representation of S_3 .

- $\lambda = (1, 1, 1)$:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{(1,1,1)} &= \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma)e_\sigma \rightarrow V_{(1,1,1)} = \mathbb{C}S_3 \cdot c_{(1,1,1)} = \mathbb{C} \left\{ \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma)e_{\tau\sigma} : \tau \in S_3 \right\} = \\ &= \mathbb{C} \left\{ \text{sgn}(\tau) \sum_{\sigma' \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma')e_{\sigma'} : \tau \in S_3 \right\} = \mathbb{C} \sum_{\sigma' \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma')e_{\sigma'} \end{aligned}$$

We got an alternating representation of S_3 , since any $\tau \in S_3$ acts on $V_{(1,1,1)}$ by multiplying its sign:

$$\tau \cdot \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma) e_\sigma = \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma) e_{\tau\sigma} = \text{sgn}(\tau) \sum_{\sigma' \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma') e_{\sigma'}$$

Indeed, all obtained Young symmetrizers are idempotent:

$$c_{(3)}^2 = \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} e_\sigma \cdot \sum_{\tau \in S_3} e_\tau = \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \sum_{\tau \in S_3} e_{\sigma\tau} = \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \sum_{\sigma' \in S_3} e_{\sigma'} = 6 \cdot c_{(3)}$$

$$c_{(2,1)}^2 = (e_1 + e_{(12)} - e_{(13)} - e_{(132)}) \cdot (e_1 + e_{(12)} - e_{(13)} - e_{(132)}) = 3 \cdot c_{(2,1)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_{(1,1,1)}^2 &= \left(\sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma) e_\sigma \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{\tau \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\tau) e_\tau \right) = \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \sum_{\tau \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma\tau) e_{\sigma\tau} = \\ &= \sum_{\sigma \in S_3} \sum_{\sigma' \in S_3} \text{sgn}(\sigma') e_{\sigma'} = 6 \cdot c_{(1,1,1)} \end{aligned}$$

As denoted in lemma 2.2.3 as $c_\lambda^2 = \frac{n!}{\dim V_\lambda} c_\lambda$, $\frac{n!}{\dim V_\lambda}$ depends on the Young diagram λ . In fact, to denote λ the conjugacy class S_n .

2.3 The dihedral group D_n

This is a group of rotations and reflections of the plane which preserve a regular polygon with n vertices. It contains n rotations that form a subgroup isomorphic to C_n and n reflections. Its order is $2n$. If we denote by r the rotation through an angle $\frac{2\pi}{n}$ and if s is any one of the reflections, then we have:

$$r^n = 1, \quad s^2 = 1, \quad srs = r^{-1}.$$

Each element of the group D_n is written uniquely, either in the form r^k , with $0 \leq k \leq n-1$ (if it belongs to C_n), or in the form sr^k , with $0 \leq k \leq n-1$ (if it does not belong to C_n). Note that the relation $srs = r^{-1}$ implies the relation $sr^k s = r^{-k}$, whence $(sr^k)^2 = 1$.

Realization of D_n as a group of rigid of three-dimensional space.

There are several implementations.

1. The usual realization (traditional notation D_n). Rotations are realized as rotations around the axis $0z$, and for reflections, the reflections through n lines in the $0xy$ plane. These lines form angles with each other equal to $\frac{\pi}{n}$.

2. The realization by means of the C_{nv} group. Here, instead of the reflections with respect to the *lines* in the $0xy$ plane, we take reflections with respect to *planes* passing through the $0z$ axis.

3. The \$D_{2n}\$ group can be realized as the \$D_{nh}\$ group.

Irreducible representations of the group \$D_n\$ (\$n \ge 1\$ is even).

First of all, there are 4 representations of degree 1, which associate the elements \$r\$ and \$s\$ with the numbers \$\pm 1\$ in all possible ways. Their characters \$\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \psi_4\$ are given by the following table:

	\$r^k\$	\$sr^k\$
\$\psi_1\$	1	1
\$\psi_2\$	1	-1
\$\psi_3\$	\$(-1)^k\$	\$(-1)^k\$
\$\psi_4\$	\$(-1)^k\$	\$(-1)^{k+1}\$

Let us go over to the description of the representation of the degree 2. Put \$w = e^{2\pi i/n}\$, and let \$k\$ be an arbitrary integer. We define a representation \$\rho^h\$ of the group \$D_n\$ by setting

$$\rho^h(r^k) = \begin{pmatrix} w^{hk} & 0 \\ 0 & w^{-hk} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \rho^h(sr^k) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & w^{-hk} \\ w^{hk} & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Directly verifies that it is indeed a *representation*. It depends only on the class \$h\$ modulo \$n\$. Moreover, the representations \$\rho^h\$ and \$\rho^{n-h}\$ are isomorphic. Therefore, we can assume that \$0 \le h \le n/2\$. We are not interested in the cases \$h = 0\$ and \$h = n/2\$, since reducible representations correspond to them. On the contrary, for \$0 < h < n/2\$ the representation \$\rho^h\$ is *irreducible*: indeed, since \$w^h \neq w^{-h}\$, the only invariant lines with respect to \$\rho^h(r)\$ will be the coordinate axes, but they are not invariant under \$\rho^h(s)\$. Similar reasoning shows that all these representations are pairwise non-isomorphic. The corresponding characters are given by the formulas

$$\chi_h(r^k) = w^{hk} + w^{-hk} = 2 \cos \frac{2\pi hk}{n},$$

$$\chi_h(sr^k) = 0.$$

The irreducible representations of degrees 1 and 2 constructed above exhaust all *irreducible representations* of the group \$D_n\$ (up to isomorphism). Indeed, the sum of the squares of their degrees is \$4 \times 1 + \left(\frac{n}{2} - 1\right) \times 4 = 2n\$, which, as you know, is the order of the group \$D_n\$.

Example 2.3.1 *The group \$D_6\$ has 4 representations of degree 1 with characters \$\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \psi_4\$ and two irreducible representations of degree 2 with characters \$\chi_1\$ and \$\chi_2\$.*

Irreducible representations of the group \$D_n\$ (\$n\$ is odd).

There are only 2 representations of degree 1 with the characters \$\psi_1\$ and \$\psi_2\$, as shown in the following table:

	\$r^k\$	\$sr^k\$
\$\psi_1\$	1	1
\$\psi_2\$	1	-1

The representations ρ^h of degree 2 are defined by the same formulas as in the case of even n . For $0 < h < n/2$ they are irreducible and pairwise non-isomorphic (note that the condition $h < n/2$, since n is odd, can also be written in the form $h \leq n - 1/2$). The formulas for the characters remain the same.

The indicated representations exhaust the *all irreducible representations* of the group D_n , since the sum of the squares of their degrees is $2 \times 1 + \frac{n-1}{2} 4 = 2n$, which is equal to the order of the group D_n .

Chapter 3

Young's symmetrizer

For the general notation of a seminormal representation, see [28]. In this section, I will formulate it for S_k in convenient terms (see [26]).

Let S_k be a symmetric group on k symbols, $e_{ij} \in S_k$ transposition. The Jucys-Murphy elements are defined as follows (see [22], [25]):

$$x_1 = 0, \quad x_2 = e_{12}, \quad x_3 = e_{13} + e_{23}, \dots, \quad x_k = e_{1k} + e_{2k} + \dots + e_{k-1,k}.$$

As in [24], we will identify the Partitions λ of a positive integer k with a Young diagram of k cells. *Young table of the form λ* is the Young diagram corresponding to λ , filled in with the integers from 1 to k . A tableau is called a *standard* one if the numbers that fill it do not decrease along the rows from left to right and along the columns downwards.

For any partition λ denote by $\mathcal{T}(\lambda)$ the set of standard tableaux of shape λ . For $\Lambda \in \mathcal{T}(\lambda)$ and $1 \leq p \leq k$, put $c_\Lambda(p) = j - i$, where (i, j) is the slot in Λ occupied by p .

Theorem 3.0.1 ([25], [26], [28]). *Let S^λ be the irreducible representation of S_k corresponding to the partition λ . Then in S^λ there exist a common eigenbasis for the Jucys-Murphy elements $x_1, \dots, x_k$; the basis can be indexed with $\mathcal{T}(\lambda)$ as follows:*

$$x_p v_\Lambda = c_\Lambda(p) v_\Lambda, \quad \text{for all } \Lambda \in \mathcal{T}(\lambda) \text{ and } 1 \leq p \leq k.$$

Let us partially order partitions with respect to *dominance*, i.e., we set

$$\mu \geq \lambda \iff \sum_{i=1}^l \mu_i \geq \sum_{i=1}^l \lambda_i \quad \text{for } l = 1, 2, \dots.$$

Let Λ_c be a Young tableau of shape λ , consecutively filled in along the columns (that is where the subscript comes from) from left to right. Set

$$(3.1) \quad \kappa_{\Lambda_c} = \prod_{i=1}^k (j - x_i),$$

where j is the number of the column occupied by i . Since the elements $x_1, \dots, x_k$ pairwise commute, the order of the factors in (3.1) is irrelevant.

Example 3.0.2 For

$$\Lambda_c = \begin{array}{ccc} 1 & 4 & 7 \\ 2 & 5 & 8 \\ 3 & 6 & \end{array}$$

we have

$$\kappa_{\Lambda_c} = 1 \cdot (1 - x_2)(1 - x_3)(2 - x_4)(2 - x_5)(2 - x_6)(3 - x_7)(3 - x_8).$$

Theorem 3.0.3 Let S^μ be the irreducible representation of S_k corresponding to a partition μ of k . Then

i) $\kappa_{\Lambda_c}(S^\mu) = 0$ if $\mu > \Lambda_c$;

ii) $\kappa_{\Lambda_c}(v_\Lambda) = 0$ if $\Lambda_c \neq \Lambda$ for $\Lambda \in \mathcal{T}(\lambda)$ and the basis vectors v_{Λ_c} as in theorem 3.0.1;

iii) $\kappa_{\Lambda_c}(v_{\Lambda_c}) = 1^{\lambda_1} 2^{\lambda_2} \dots n^{\lambda_n} v_{\Lambda_c}$, where $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_n$ are nonzero integers of the partition λ .

Proof: Let $\mu \geq \lambda$ and Λ be a standard tableau of shape μ ; let $v_\lambda \in S^\mu$ be the corresponding vector for the seminormal basis. If $\Lambda \neq \Lambda_c$, then there exist a j such that the j -th columns of the tableau Λ and Λ_c are distinct whereas all the columns with lesser numbers are identical. Since the orders of the tableaux coincide and $\mu \geq \lambda$, it follows that $\mu'_j \leq \lambda'_j$ (these are the lengths of the j -columns of the tableaux Λ and Λ_c , respectively).

Let p be the least of the numbers from the j -th column of Λ (such a number exists because $\Lambda \neq \Lambda_c$ and $\mu'_j \leq \lambda'_j$). Since Λ is standard, the slot that p occupies is $(1, j + 1)$. Hence,

$$x_p v_\Lambda = c_\Lambda(p) v_\Lambda = (j + 1 - 1) v_s = j v_\Lambda, \quad \text{i.e., } (j - x_p) v_\Lambda = 0.$$

Since $j - x_p$ enters κ_{Λ_c} as a factor, $\kappa_{\Lambda_c} v_\Lambda = 0$. This proves i) and ii). To prove iii), observe that

$$(j - x_p) v_{\Lambda_c} = (j - (j - i)) v_{\Lambda_c} = i v_{\Lambda_c},$$

where i is the number of the row occupied by x_p . This proves iii). ■

Lemma 3.0.4 Let $p < k$ and let S_p be considered as a subgroup of the group S_k , that preserves all but the first p symbols. Let U be a S_k -module, ε the nontrivial one-dimensional representation and $b = \sum_{\sigma \in S_p} \varepsilon(\sigma) \sigma$, where $\varepsilon(\sigma)$

denotes sign σ . Let $v \in U$ be a nonzero vector, fixed by transposition e_{lk} for $l \leq p$. Then

$$b\left(\sum_{i \in S_p} e_{ik}\right)v = bv.$$

Proof: Let $P = \{1, \dots, p\}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} b\left(\sum_{i \in P} e_{ik}\right)v &= b\left(\sum_{i \in P} e_{ik}\right)e_{lk}v \\ &= b\left(1 + \sum_{i \in P \setminus \{l\}} e_{ik}e_{kl}\right)v = b\left(1 + \sum_{i \in P \setminus \{l\}} e_{li}e_{ik}\right)v \\ &= b\left(1 - \sum_{i \in P \setminus \{l\}} e_{ik}\right)v = b\left(2 - \sum_{i \in P} e_{ik}\right)v; \end{aligned}$$

hence,, $b\left(\sum_{i \in P} e_{ik}\right)v = bv$. ■

Corollary 3.0.5 *Let R_{Λ_c} , and C_{Λ_c} be the row and column stabilizers of the tableau Λ_c ; let U be a S_k -module, and $v \in U$ a nonzero R_{Λ_c} -invariant vector. Set $b_{\Lambda_c} = \sum_{\sigma \in C_{\Lambda_c}} \varepsilon(\sigma)\sigma$. Then $\kappa_{\Lambda_c}v = b_{\Lambda_c}v$.*

Proof: Induction on the number of columns in Λ_c . If Λ_c consist of one column, then by induction on k we can easily verify the identity

$$(1 - e_{12})(1 - e_{13} - e_{23}) \cdots (1 - e_{1k} - \cdots - e_{k-1,k}) = \sum_{\sigma \in S_k} \varepsilon(\sigma)\sigma.$$

So, for one column, the statement is true.

Let the tableau Λ_c consist of n columns $\Lambda_1, \dots, \Lambda_n$; let Λ_c^* be obtained from Λ_c by deleting the last column. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_{\Lambda_c}v &= \kappa_{\Lambda_c^*} \prod_{i \in \Lambda_n} (n - x_i)v = \prod_{i \in \Lambda_n} (n - x_i) \cdot \kappa_{\Lambda_c^*}v \\ &= (\text{by induction}) = \prod_{i \in \Lambda_n} (n - x_i) \cdot b_{\Lambda_c^*}v = b_{\Lambda_c^*} \prod_{i \in \Lambda_n} (n - x_i)v. \end{aligned}$$

Let $i \in \Lambda_n$; then

$$b_{\Lambda_c^*}(n - x_i)v = b_{\Lambda_c^*}\left(n - \sum_{\sigma \in \Lambda_1} e_{\sigma i} - \sum_{\sigma \in \Lambda_2} e_{\sigma i} - \cdots - \sum_{\sigma \in \Lambda_n, \alpha < i} e_{\sigma i}\right)v.$$

By lemma 3.0.4 $b_{\Lambda_c^*}\left(\sum_{\sigma \in \Lambda_j} e_{\sigma i}\right)v = b_{\Lambda_c^*}v$ for $j = 1, \dots, n-1$, therefore $b_{\Lambda_c^*}(n - x_i)v = b_{\Lambda_c^*}\left(1 - \sum_{\alpha \in \Lambda_n, \alpha < i} e_{\alpha i}\right)v$. Hence, if $\Lambda_n = \{i, i+1, \dots, i+l\}$, then

$$\begin{aligned}\kappa_{\Lambda_c} v &= b_{\Lambda_c^*} (1 - e_{i,i+1})(1 - e_{i,i+2} - e_{i+1,i+2}) \cdots (1 - e_{i,i+l} - \cdots - e_{i+l-1,i+l}) v \\ &= b_{\Lambda_c^*} \left(\sum_{\sigma \in \Lambda_n} \varepsilon(\sigma) \sigma \right) v = b_{\Lambda_c} v.\end{aligned}$$

■

Thus, if $v = \sum_{\sigma \in R_{\Lambda_c}} \sigma = a_{\Lambda_c}$, then

$$c_{\Lambda_c} = b_{\Lambda_c} a_{\Lambda_c} = \kappa_{\Lambda_c} a_{\Lambda_c},$$

those. we have expressed the Young symmetrizer c_{Λ_c} as $\kappa_{\Lambda_c} a_{\Lambda_c}$.

Conclusions

The theory of *group representations* deals with the classification of homomorphisms of the abstract group G into linear transformation groups or matrix groups. In this work, the theory of representations of finite groups in finite-dimensional vector spaces was developed.

In this work, we introduced the basic definitions of the theory of group representations and provided examples to illustrate them. We also talked about the characters of representations, Schur's lemma, etc. We also studied irreducible representations of the symmetric group S_n based on the Young symmetrizer technique.

Having studied the foundations of the theory of group representations and irreducible representations of the symmetric group, a new method was developed for obtaining the Young symmetrizer for a symmetric group.

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